

Accelerating Medicines Partnership®
SCHIZOPHRENIA

AMP SCZ Reference Manual

Release 4.0

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Accelerating Medicines Partnership®

SCHIZOPHRENIA

Overview

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

How to cite this dataset in publications:

"The dataset used in this study was generated by the Accelerating Medicines Partnership® Schizophrenia Program (Wannan et al., 2024) and downloaded from the NIMH Data Archive (data release 4.0 doi: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136))"

General comment:

Please note that all data is subject to change between releases. Always use the latest release for the most up-to-date information.

Change Log:

- Participant count: now includes 2438 unique participants.
- Visits included extend up to month 5.
- Participant and data selection criteria changed to exclude participants who did not have baseline measures.
- Visit IDs added to each instrument.
- ndar_subject01 phenotype now has a new group: HHR. A few participants were recruited as healthy controls but later met the criteria for CHR. We gave them a new phenotype because we want people to be cautious when using them as controls.

Selection criteria:

- **Criteria to include a participant in this data release:**
 - They have a valid GUID and age,
 - They fulfill the study inclusion criteria (`chrcrit_included == 1`),
 - The study inclusion form has no QC issues.
 - If the participant is a CHR, the participant has to fulfill the criteria for the SIPS and/or CAARMS groups.
 - If the participant is an HC, the participant does not fulfill the criteria of any of the SIPS and CAARMS groups.
 - The screening PSYCHS forms have no QC issues.

- They have completed at least one baseline measure.
- About 10% of these participants are held out from the NDA dataset for future validation of prediction and subtyping algorithms.
- **Form data Quality Control and selection criteria.**

A form will be checked by the automatic quality control (QC) program if it is marked as complete and not marked as missing by the raters. General checks, such as searching for required fields that were left blank or extreme outliers in numerical variables, are applied to nearly every form. More specific QC checks are also applied to individual forms.

For example, certain cognitive measures, such as IQ assessments, are checked to make sure that raw scores are properly converted to standardized scores. Participant age at the time of the assessment is estimated based on the interview date that was entered and the date that their demographic data was collected. This information is then used to recalculate their T-Scores and FSIQ scores from the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence (WASI) conversion tables. If these recalculated scores do not match what was entered by the raters, they are added to the QC trackers to be corrected.

Fluid biomarkers also include a multitude of additional checks to ensure that values fall within reasonable ranges and barcodes are entered properly. This includes scanning the database for volumes that exceed 1.1 millimeters, blood draw dates that are entered as being later than the dates that the vials were sent to the lab, processing times that exceed 480 minutes, and more. Rack barcodes are also checked to make sure they are in the proper formats and are not duplicated between participants.

Most forms undergo QC with the goal of only sending queries that can be corrected to the data collection sites. However, certain forms, such as self-report forms, are not able to be fixed post-hoc. Data entry errors for these forms are recorded for network heads to be aware of but are not sent directly to raters to fix.

A form will only be uploaded **if it is marked complete, has no outstanding QC queries**, and the participant does not have any issues detected with their inclusion status or cohort assignment (see above).

Each form and data domain has its own selection criteria documented in the relevant manual.

Known Issues:

This release has a few known issues, which are documented in the data manuals for each assessment domain. Key issues include:

- **Clinical Measures:**
 - **PGI-S Scale Inconsistency:** ProNET and PRESCIENT utilize different rating scales (4-point vs. 5-point), creating anchoring bias that makes scores like "4" incomparable across networks. To address this, it is recommended to collapse higher scores into a single "Moderate to Severe" category to ensure a stable distribution for cross-network analysis.

- **ASSIST Branching Logic Discrepancy:** Differences in how substance use questions are triggered resulted in significantly more missing data (NAs) in PRESCIENT compared to ProNET, specifically regarding concerns expressed by others. Analysts can mitigate this by restricting past-month severity evaluations to only those participants who reported active substance use during that period.
- **PSYCHS and BPRS Calibration:** While both measure psychotic symptoms, the PSYCHS is a specialized tool for clinical high risk (CHR) detection, whereas the BPRS is a general measure that lacks the frequency and tenacity anchors necessary for CHR assessment. Because these tools serve different purposes and show wide site-specific variability, they should be viewed as complementary rather than interchangeable.
- **MRI Data:**
 - **Consent Date Technical Error:** Baseline sessions for three participants were excluded from this release due errors in consent dates.
 - **Pipeline & Processing Warnings:** FreeSurfer outputs have not undergone manual editing or visual quality control (QC). Additionally, reconstructions were not optimized for high-resolution processing and do not fully leverage the sub-1 mm spatial resolution of the T1w and T2w images. Users should prioritize SynthSeg-derived total intracranial volume over default eTIV estimates, which are often unreliable due to Talairach transform failures.
 - **FreeSurfer Data Exclusions:** Longitudinal FreeSurfer outputs for five specific subjects must be excluded from all analyses because an incorrect session was used to generate their "base" templates, rendering all resulting timepoints invalid. Furthermore, specific longitudinal timepoints are unavailable for 15 additional subjects because processing failed for those sessions despite a template being present.
- **Digital Biomarkers:**
 - **Smartphone Data:** Due to technical issues with the PRESCIENT MindLAMP server in transferring data transfer to the NDA database, the passive sensing data from August 2023 onward is not included in this release but will be added in future updates.
- **Cognitive Measures:** A scoring issue with Penn CNB task SVOLT-B and a bug causing incorrect logging of responses on some SPLLT were identified and corrected. Some follow-up SPLLT data is unrecoverable and has been removed.

For more details on these and other domain-specific issues, please refer to the '**Known Issues**' section in the data manual for the corresponding measurement.

No known issues were reported at this time for EEG, Digital Biomarkers: Actigraphy, Language Sampling Data, and Fluid Biomarkers.

Background and Rationale

Though early intervention and treatment is linked to improved long-term health, few tools currently exist to identify people who are at early risk of developing schizophrenia. The Accelerating Medicines Partnership (AMP®) SCZ program aims to generate tools that will

fast-track the development of effective, early-stage treatments for people who are at risk for schizophrenia.

The AMP SCZ program goals include:

1. Developing tools for predicting individual outcomes
The AMP SCZ program aims to identify measurable indicators of illness, known as biomarkers, that can be used to predict the likelihood of progression to psychosis and other health outcomes. These biomarkers will help researchers study how well treatments work for different groups of people.
2. Establishing a global research network
The AMP SCZ program will establish an international research network focused on recruiting young people who are at clinical high risk for schizophrenia. The AMP SCZ program aims to recruit nearly 2,500 participants, ages 12-30, from 42 study sites around the world. The project's large, international scope will ensure that AMP SCZ program findings apply broadly and are not specific to one place or one group of people.
3. Setting the stage for testing new preventive treatments
The AMP SCZ program will create a research framework that can help researchers design better clinical trials, develop better approaches for measuring treatment response, and create better tools for detecting early-stage risk. This framework will provide a foundation for the development of faster, more effective treatments.
4. Creating an accessible data repository
Research data from the AMP SCZ program will be available to the broader scientific community through the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) Data Archive. Providing access to AMP SCZ program data will allow researchers to translate findings into key tools and enable testing of therapies quickly and efficiently.

Dataset and Overview

The May 2026 AMP-SCZ Release on NDA contains fully quality-controlled screening, baseline through month 2 data. The following subject numbers are:

- Unique subjects: **2438**
- Clinical measures: up to **2438**, depending on the measure.
- Cognitive measures, depending on the measure:
 - IQ measures Baseline only: **2291**
 - PennCNB measures Baseline only: **2150**
- Electroencephalography (EEG): **2228**
- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI): **2088**
- Interview transcripts:
 - Open interview: **1561**
 - PSYCHS: **726**
- Raw actigraphy watch data: **916**
- Smartphone surveys: **1603**
- Smartphone data (Screen use, accelerometry, geolocation): **1145**
- Fluid biomarkers: **2290**

Please refer to the spreadsheet "[ampscz-release-4.0-record.csv](#)" for data availability for each measure per subject under 'Files'. For detailed information on NDA variable short names, please refer to the "[nda_vars.csv](#)" codebook under 'Files'.

Please note that information on subject phenotype, including clinical high risk for psychosis or community control, is available in the [ndar_subject01](#) instrument.

Clinical Research Sites

Clinical Research sites stem from two research networks, PRESCIENT and ProNET, supported by a central coordination center, PREDICT-DPACC.

The Psychosis-Risk Outcomes Network (ProNET) comprises 26 international sites, including 17 in the United States, two in Canada, three in Europe, two in the United Kingdom, and two in Asia. The network is led by Scott Woods, M.D., Professor of Psychiatry at Yale University, with co-principal investigators Carrie Bearden, Ph.D., Professor of Psychiatry and Biobehavioral Sciences and Psychology at the University of California, Los Angeles, and John Kane, M.D., Professor and Chair of Psychiatry at the Donald and Barbara Zucker School of Medicine at Hofstra/Northwell.

The Prediction Scientific Global Consortium (PRESCIENT) comprises 16 international sites, including two in Australia, three in Asia, four in Europe, one in the United Kingdom, and one in South America. The PRESCIENT network is led by Barnaby Nelson, Ph.D., head of ultra-high risk for psychosis research at the Center for Youth Mental Health at the University of Melbourne and at Orygen, Melbourne, Australia, and Patrick McGorry, M.D., Ph.D., head of the Center for Youth Mental Health at the University of Melbourne and executive director of Orygen.

The Data Processing, Analysis, and Coordination Center (DPACC) is led by Martha E. Shenton, Ph.D., Professor of Psychiatry and Radiology at Harvard Medical School and Founding Director of the Psychiatry Neuroimaging Laboratory at Brigham and Women's Hospital, and Rene Kahn, M.D., Ph.D., Chair of the Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Health at Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai.

Study Population (Inclusion/Exclusion criteria)

Participants, either healthy controls or at clinical high risk for psychosis, will:

- Be between 12 and 30 years old.
- Be able to understand and provide informed consent to participate in this research.
- Meet criteria for clinical high risk for psychosis OR have no history of serious mental health concerns (Healthy Control).
- NOT meet criteria for some diagnoses, such as intellectual disability, certain nervous system disorders, or Traumatic Brain Injury.
- NOT have a current or past diagnosis of a psychotic disorder such as schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, or unspecified psychosis disorder.
- NOT have taken some antipsychotic medications.

Study Procedures

Study personnel were trained to administer clinical, cognitive and imaging measures at various time points throughout the duration of the study. The [Standard Operating Procedures \(SOPs\)](#) are available on Zenodo.

Clinical assessments are collected every month for the first year, then again at 18 and 24 months, and/or at the point of conversion to psychosis. Biomarker measures are collected at both baseline and two months. Digital biomarkers, including actigraphy and phone app-based data collection, are collected daily during the first year. Cognitive assessments are collected at six, 12, and 24 months, and/or at conversion to psychosis.

Collection of these biomarkers in the CHR population over time will help in establishing early indicators of pharmacologic treatment efficacy. Algorithms will be derived from machine learning and AI approaches and used to predict clinical endpoints: conversion to psychosis (primary clinical endpoint); remission of the CHR state (secondary clinical endpoint), and non-conversion/non-remission (secondary clinical endpoint).

PRESCIENT		
1	Melbourne, Australia	ME
2	Jena, Germany	JE
3	Copenhagen, Denmark	CP
4	Birmingham, UK	BM
5	Lausanne, Switzerland	LS
6	Gwangju, Korea	GW
7	Singapore	SG
8	Hong Kong	HK
9	Cologne, Germany	CG
10	Santiago, Chile	ST
ProNET		
1	UCLA	LA
2	OREGON	OR
3	Harvard/BIDMC	BI
4	NORTHWELL	NL
5	UNC	NC
6	UCSD	SD
7	Calgary	CA

8	YALE	YA
9	UCSF/Path	SF
10	Penn	PA
11	Mt.Sinai	SI
12	Pitt	PI
13	Northwestern	NN
14	UC Irvine	IR
15	Temple	TE
16	Georgia	GA
17	WashU	WU
18	Hartford	HA
19	Montreal	MT
20	King's College London	KC
21	Pavia, Italy	PV
22	Madrid	MA
23	Cambridge UK	CM
24	LMU Munich	MU
25	Seoul	SL
26	Ohio State	OH
27	University of Rochester	UR

Clinical Measures

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Change Log:

- Participants were added (now data for **2438** unique participants)
- Data include visits from screening up to and including month 5.
- Inclusion of two floating clinical forms:
 - Resource Use Log
 - Psychosocial Treatment Form
- Changes were made to the Family Interview for Genetic Studies (FIGS) scoring algorithm. Details are present at the end of the manual.

Selection criteria:

- If a clinical form has unresolved errors on the automated form QC trackers, then all variables in that form will be excluded from the upload (see overview document for more details).

Known Issues for Release 4.0:

- There are differences in the **Patient Global Impression Scale – Severity (PGI-S)** coding between ProNET and PRESCIENT sites.
 - ProNET sites used a 4-point scale ranging from 1 (Normal/No symptoms) to 4 (Severe) whereas PRESCIENT sites used a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (Normal/No symptoms) to 5 (Very severe).
 - Therefore, participants that were rated a score of 4 (“Severe”) may not be directly comparable between networks as 4 represents the highest possible score for ProNET and the second-highest score for PRESCIENT. Participants may also have completed the scale differently if it had a different range. This anchoring bias is a limitation to the data that we cannot mathematically correct and should be taken into consideration when interpreting the results.
 - **Recommendation:** *Although there is no way to address the larger issue that there may be rating differences between the networks if the highest score is 4 versus if it’s 5, we advise users who want to use the PGI-S to combine scores of 3, 4, or 5 with “3.”* This will ensure that the scales of the PGI-S are the same

across both networks, representing one “Moderate to Severe” value. This method ensures the most stable distribution across networks.

- There is a **branching logic difference** in the assist01 between **PRESCIENT** and **ProNET**:
 - In **PRESCIENT**, if a participant reported **lifetime use** of a substance (chrassist_whoassist_useX = 1) but **no use in the past month** (chrassist_whoassist_oftenX = 0), then question Q6 — *“Has a friend or relative or anyone else ever expressed concern about your use of (substance)?”*(chrassist_whoassist_concernX) — was **automatically skipped and coded as missing (NA)**. This difference also contributes to more missing data in PRESCIENT for severity variables chrassist_substance1, chrassist_substance2, etc.
 - In **ProNET**, raters asked this question **regardless of** past-month use (chrassist_whoassist_oftenX), resulting in fewer missing values.
 - One way to address this discrepancy in analyses is to restrict past-month severity analyses to participants who reported any substance use in the past month.
- **Calibration between PSYCHS and BPRS symptom ratings**
 - The PSYCHS (Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS; Woods et al., 2024) and Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS; Overall & Gorham, 1962) each measure psychotic-like symptoms **but they should not be interpreted interchangeably or assumed to map directly onto one another**. Rather, they are complementary measures capturing different dimensions of psychopathology.
 - The PSYCHS (Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS; Woods et al., 2024) is a semi-structured clinical interview developed specifically to identify and assess individuals at clinical high risk (CHR) for psychosis. It harmonizes elements from the CAARMS (Comprehensive Assessment of At-Risk Mental States) and SIPS (Structured Interview for Psychosis-Risk Syndromes) instruments to create a single, unified measure that ensures consistent CHR assessment across studies and clinical sites. The PSYCHS evaluates symptom domains including attenuated delusions, attenuated hallucinations, attenuated disorganization, and attenuated thought disorder, captured through 15 positive symptom items. Each PSYCHS symptom is rated on a six-point scale across multiple dimensions, including symptom description, tenacity, distress, and interference with thoughts, emotions, social interactions, or behavior. This detailed, structured approach allows the PSYCHS to capture **subthreshold positive psychotic experiences** with sensitivity, making it particularly well suited for assessing CHR individuals and tracking symptom progression over time. In the AMP SCZ study, the PSYCHS serves as the gold standard for assessing CHR symptoms, determining study inclusion, and rating key outcomes such as conversion to psychosis and the severity of attenuated positive symptoms at critical time points. Its comprehensive anchors, including intensity, frequency, duration, conviction, and distress, increase the

sensitivity of evaluating subtle prodromal symptoms and further support reliable longitudinal monitoring of CHR symptoms.

- In contrast, the Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) is a widely used instrument for assessing **general psychopathology** (Overall & Gorham, 1962). It evaluates a broad range of symptoms, including psychotic features (hallucinations, unusual thought content, delusions, conceptual disorganization, suspiciousness), affective symptoms (anxiety, depression, guilt, tension), behavioral and activation symptoms (hostility, uncooperativeness, excitement), motor symptoms (motor retardation), and somatic concerns, including blunted affect. Each symptom is rated on a seven-point scale, providing a quantitative measure of overall severity. The BPRS is commonly applied in schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, mood disorders with psychotic features, and other psychiatric populations. Unlike the PSYCHS, however, the **BPRS was not designed to detect subtle, subthreshold psychotic experiences or to assess CHR symptoms.**
- Importantly, the BPRS **does not formally incorporate dimensions critical to CHR assessment, such as symptom frequency or tenacity.** Consequently, high BPRS scores on positive symptom items do not necessarily indicate prodromal or CHR-level psychosis. In AMP SCZ, no formal calibration was performed to map sub-CHR, CHR-level, or fully psychotic symptoms onto the BPRS 7-point scale. A comparison of Suspiciousness ratings between the PSYCHS and BPRS, administered within one week, showed a moderately strong overall correlation ($r = 0.71$), but site-specific correlations ranged widely (r range 0.24–0.89), reflecting variability in how the BPRS was applied relative to the PSYCHS. Some sites also rated symptoms as fully psychotic on the BPRS even when the PSYCHS indicated no conversion to psychosis, while other sites rated CHR-level symptoms as very mild on the BPRS despite their prodromal significance on the PSYCHS. These findings highlight that, although the BPRS shows moderate convergent validity with the PSYCHS on certain items, it is a complementary tool rather than a definitive measure for CHR assessment.
- In summary, while the BPRS is valuable for tracking broad symptom changes over time, the PSYCHS is precisely tailored for identifying and monitoring CHR symptoms and determining conversion to psychosis. The two instruments serve distinct purposes: the PSYCHS provides diagnostic precision and sensitivity for CHR, whereas the BPRS provides a general overview of symptom severity and change over time. **They should not be interpreted interchangeably or assumed to map directly onto one another, but rather as complementary measures capturing different dimensions of psychopathology.** The most important point is that the PSYCHS is the superior tool for CHR determination and conversion assessment, while the BPRS serves as a longitudinal monitoring instrument for overall psychiatric symptomatology.
- **References**
 - Overall, J. E., & Gorham, D. R. (1962). The Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale. *Psychological Reports*, 10, 799–812.

- Woods, S. W., Parker, S., Kerr, M. J., Walsh, B. C., Wijtenburg, S. A., Prunier, N., Nunez, A. R., Buccilli, K., Mourgues Codern, C., Brummitt, K., Kinney, K. S., Trankler, C., Szacilo, J., Colton, B. L., Ali, M., Haidar, A., Billah, T., Huynh, K., Ahmed, U., Adery, L. L., ... Yung, A. R. (2024). Development of the PSYCHS: Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, 18(4), 255–272.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Clinical Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for Clinical Data Acquisition in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10671419>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
Alcohol, Smoking, and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST)	assist01
Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS)	bprs01
Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS)	clgry01
Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) (Baseline)	cssrs01
8-Item Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) for Sleep	sri01
Family Interview for Genetic Studies (FIGS)	figs01
Global Functioning: Social Scale	gfs01
Global Functioning: Role Scale	gfs01
Health Conditions (Genetics and Fluid Biomarkers)	ampsc_z_hcgfb01
Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria Review	iec01
Lifetime Antipsychotic Exposure Screen	ampsc_z_lapes01
Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR)	ampsc_z_nsipr01
Overall Anxiety Severity and Impairment Scale (OASIS)	oasis01
Past Pharmaceutical Treatment	medhi01
Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)	pss01
Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS	ampsc_z_psychs01
Perceived Discrimination Scale	ampsc_z_dim01

Premorbid Adjustment Scale (PAS)	pmod01
Psychosis Polyrisk Score	ampscz_pps01
Pubertal Development Scale	pds01
Research Assistant (RA) Prediction	ampscz_rap01
Recruitment Source	ampscz_rs01
Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 (SCID-5)	scidcls01
The Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 Personality Disorders (SCID-5-PD): Schizotypal Personality Disorder Module	scidvapd01
Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) (Screening)	dsm_iv_es01
Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) (Follow-up)	dsm_iv_es01
Sociodemographics	socdem01
The Patient Global Impression Scale – Severity (PGI-S)	cgis01
Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) (Screening)	tbi01
Resource Use Log	resource_use01
Psychosocial Treatment Form	psycho_treat01

General Information

The clinical protocol consists of a wide range of instruments selected based on the consensus of leading experts in the field of clinical high-risk for psychosis. Selection criteria included construct validity, reliability, and sensitivity. Whenever available, instruments were selected and were validated, particularly for the clinical high-risk population.

The comprehensive assessment protocol provides measures of several domains relevant to the clinical high-risk for psychosis state.

Measures used at the screen define the clinical high-risk for psychosis status at screening based on attenuated psychotic symptoms, family history of psychotic disorders, and social and occupational functioning (Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS), FIGS, SOFAS). Additional scales record inclusion and exclusion criteria. Attenuated psychotic symptoms are assessed using the PSYCHS at repeated time points throughout the follow-up assessments to monitor for transition to psychosis as the study's primary endpoint. Critical secondary outcomes include persistence and remission of the clinical high-risk state for psychosis and are assessed at the follow-up assessments with the PSYCHS.

There are further secondary outcomes to assess symptoms, and other outcomes are not used for the definition of the clinical high-risk state but are relevant for the psychopathology of CHR individuals.

Based on previous literature, a range of potential predictors of primary and secondary outcomes, such as environmental risk factors or premorbid adjustment, were selected. Most of the measures entail predictive potential for primary and secondary endpoints but might also serve as clinical endpoints themselves, and thus, these constructs are not clearly separable.

A further criterion for tool selection was based on the multi-site study design; recruitment across several nations worldwide requires language-specific tools.

The following documentation describes the overall contents of various instruments used in the AMP-SCZ project. The instruments are available for download.

Instrument Descriptions

Alcohol, Smoking, and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST)

The Alcohol, Smoking, and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST) is a self-report measure used to evaluate substance use and related problems. Group, W. A. W. (2002). The Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST): development, reliability, and feasibility. *Addiction*, 97(9), 1183-1194.

Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS)

The Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) is a semi-structured interview used to assess several domains of participants' psychopathology. The final ratings are based on the overall clinical impressions. Overall, J. E., & Gorham, D. R. (1962). The brief psychiatric rating scale. *Psychological Reports*, 10(3), 799-812.

Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS)

The Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS) is a semi-structured interview that measures depressive symptoms across nine items and distinguishes between depressive symptoms and negative symptoms. Addington, D., Addington, J., & Maticka-Tyndale, E. (1993). Assessing depression in schizophrenia: the Calgary Depression Scale. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 163(S22), 39-44.

Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) (Baseline)

The Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) assesses suicidal ideation and behaviour by a semi-structured interview. Posner, K., Brown, G. K., Stanley, B., Brent, D. A., Yershova, K. V., Oquendo, M. A., ... & Mann, J. J. (2011). The Columbia–Suicide Severity Rating Scale: initial validity and internal consistency findings from three multisite studies with adolescents and adults. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 168(12), 1266-1277.

8-Item Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) for Sleep

The 8-item Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) for sleep is a self-report measure of participants' perceptions of their sleep quality, depth and restoration within the past seven days prior to assessment. It includes reporting perceived difficulties falling asleep, staying asleep as well as satisfaction with sleep. Yu, L., Buysse, D. J., Germain, A., Moul, D. E., Stover, A., Dodds, N. E., ... & Pilkonis, P. A. (2012). Development of short forms from the PROMIS™ sleep disturbance and sleep-related impairment item banks. *Behavioral Sleep Medicine*, 10(1), 6-24.

Family Interview for Genetic Studies (FIGS)

The Family Interview for Genetic Studies (FIGS) is a semi-structured interview administered to collect information about mental illnesses of any first degree relative of the participants. Second hand information might be used as well. Maxwell, M. E. (1992). Manual for the family interview for genetic studies (FIGS). Bethesda, MD: National Institute of Mental Health.

Global Functioning: Social Scale

The Global Functioning: Social Scale assesses peer relationships/conflicts, age-appropriate intimate relationship and family involvement. The rating is based on the impression the interviewer gains during an unstructured interview. Final scores are rated by the interviewer for three different timepoints: 1) current level, 2) highest and 3) lowest level in the past year prior assessment. Cornblatt, B. A., Auther, A. M., Niendam, T., Smith, C. W., Zinberg, J., Bearden, C. E., & Cannon, T. D. (2007). Preliminary findings for two new measures of social and role functioning in the prodromal phase of schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 33(3), 688-702.

Global Functioning: Role Scale

The Global Functioning: Role Scale rates the level of support provided within the participant's environment and the performance given such support (could be related to e.g., school, work). The rating is based on the impression the interviewer gains during an unstructured interview. Final scores are rated by the interviewer for three different timepoints: 1) current level, 2) highest and 3) lowest level in the past year prior assessment. Cornblatt, B. A., Auther, A. M., Niendam, T., Smith, C. W., Zinberg, J., Bearden, C. E., & Cannon, T. D. (2007). Preliminary findings for two new measures of social and role functioning in the prodromal phase of schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 33(3), 688-702.

Health Conditions (Genetics and Fluid Biomarkers)

The Health Conditions questionnaire records medical conditions or health issues via an interview with the participants and a review of medical records if available. At each follow-up visit, the presence of pre-existing conditions is reevaluated.

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria Review

While filling out the inclusion/exclusion criteria review, the interviewer provides information relevant to inclusion/exclusion about the participant and double-checks all automatically calculated values derived from other questionnaires.

Lifetime Antipsychotic Exposure Screen

The Lifetime Antipsychotic Exposure Screen lists generic antipsychotic agents for assessing lifetime antipsychotic exposure. Participants report any intake of antipsychotics. If a participant reports lifetime antipsychotic intake, the interviewer records detailed documentation.

Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR)

The Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR) is a semi-structured interview designed for use in CHR populations that measures negative symptoms in five domains, i.e., anhedonia, avolition, asociality, alogia and blunted affect. Strauss, G. P., Walker, E. F., Pelletier-Baldelli, A., Carter, N. T., Ellman, L. M., Schiffman, J., ... & Mittal, V. A. (2023). Development and Validation of the Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, sbad038.

Overall Anxiety Severity and Impairment Scale (OASIS)

The Overall Anxiety Severity and Impairment Scale (OASIS) is a self-report measure used to assess the severity of anxiety. Norman, S. B., Hami Cissell, S., Means-Christensen, A. J., & Stein, M. B. (2006). Development and validation of an overall anxiety severity and impairment scale (OASIS). *Depression and Anxiety*, 23(4), 245-249.

Past Pharmaceutical Treatment

A history of past psychiatric medication use (including antipsychotic, antidepressants, mood stabilizers, stimulants, benzodiazepines, birth control, and hormone therapy), is administered at the screening visit. All medications should have been discontinued before the screening visit. Medication frequency, dosage, indication, and compliance across course(s) are recorded.

Perceived Stress Scale

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is a self-report measure that captures the degree to which participant's appraise situations in their life as stressful. Items capture how unpredictable, uncontrollable and overloaded participants experience their lives. Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 385-396.

Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) Screen P1-P8

The semi-structured Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) interview is administered to determine whether the participant meets any clinical high-risk criteria at study inclusion. Ratings of presence, frequency, duration, and severity of positive psychotic symptoms define the actual status of the participant. Woods, S. W., Parker, S., Kerr, M. J., Walsh, B. C., Wijtenburg, S. A., Prunier, N., ... & Accelerating Medicines Partnership Schizophrenia. (2023). Development of the PSYCHS: Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS. medRxiv, 2023-04.

Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) Screen P9-AC32

The semi-structured Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) interview is administered to determine whether the participant meets any clinical high-risk criteria at study inclusion. Ratings of presence, frequency, duration, and severity of positive psychotic symptoms define the actual status of the participant. The second part of the PSYCHS includes the final clinical high-risk diagnoses. Woods, S. W., Parker, S., Kerr, M. J., Walsh, B. C., Wijtenburg, S. A., Prunier, N., ... & Accelerating Medicines Partnership Schizophrenia. (2023). Development of the PSYCHS: Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS. medRxiv, 2023-04.

Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) Follow-up

At follow up, interviewers complete the PSYCHS to determine whether any symptoms or the clinical high-risk status of the participants have changed.

Positive Symptoms CAARMS Harmonized with SIPS (PSYCHS) AV recording run sheet

If participants consent, a portion of the PSYCHS interview is audio and/or video recorded to assist ratings and quality assurance. It might be incorporated into speech and facial expression analyses. The PSYCHS AV recording run sheet provides meta-information about the interview and the quality and recording conditions.

Perceived Discrimination Scale

Based on Janssen et al., (2003) participants are asked several questions to determine whether they have experienced discrimination in their lifetime. Janssen, I., Hanssen, M., Bak, M., Bijl, R., De Graaf, R., Vollebergh, W., McKenzie, K., & Van Os, J. (2003). Discrimination and delusional ideation. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 182(1), 71-76.

Premorbid Adjustment Scale (PAS)

The Premorbid Adjustment Scale is a semi-structured interview used to assess premorbid functioning across developmental periods. Here, participants describe their social and role adjustment depending on their age during childhood, early adolescence, late adolescence and adulthood. van Mastrigt, S., & Addington, J. (2002). Assessment of premorbid function in first-episode schizophrenia: modifications to the Premorbid Adjustment Scale. *Journal of Psychiatry and Neuroscience*, 27(2), 92-101.

Psychosis Polyrisk Score

The Psychosis Polyrisk Score is a self-report measure used to assess known environmental risk factors for psychosis. Oliver, D., Radua, J., Reichenberg, A., Uher, R., & Fusar-Poli, P. (2019). Psychosis Polyrisk Score (PPS) is used to detect at-risk individuals and to predict their outcomes. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10, 174.

Psychosocial Treatment Form

At each visit, participants report any use of psychotherapy (e.g., supportive counseling, cognitive behavioral therapy, drug and alcohol treatment), including frequency, onset-offset dates, and study visits at which therapy was ongoing.

Pubertal Development Scale

The Pubertal Development Scale is a self-report measure used to assess physical changes during puberty. Thus, it is only assessed in participants under the age of 18. Petersen, A. C., Crockett, L., Richards, M., & Boxer, A. (1988). A self-report measure of pubertal status: Reliability, validity, and initial norms. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 17(2), 117-133.

Research Assistant (RA) Prediction

After finishing all baseline assessments, the interviewers record whether they think the participant is likely to transition to psychosis. Further, they provide information about their experience in conducting evaluations with clinical high-risk for psychosis individuals.

Recruitment Source

The interviewer records the source from which the participant was recruited for the study.

Resource Use Log

At each visit, participants report any hospitalizations that occurred since the last visit, including dates of hospitalization and reason(s) for hospitalization.

Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 (Modules A: Mood Episodes, B: Psychotic and Associated Symptoms, C: Psychotic Differential, D: Mood Differential, E: Substance Use Disorders)

The Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 (SCID-5) is a semi-structured interview used to assess diagnostic criteria for mood, psychosis, and substance use disorders. First, M. B., Williams, J. B., Karg, R. S., & Spitzer, R. L. (2015). Structured Clinical Interview for DSM—5—Research version (SCID-5 for DSM-5, research version; SCID-5-RV). Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Association, 2015, 1-94.

The Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 Personality Disorders (SCID-5-PD): Schizotypal Personality Disorder Module

The SCID-5-PD is a semi-structured interview for DSM-5 used to assess the diagnostic criteria for Schizotypal Personality Disorder, including a subset of criteria from the Paranoid Personality Disorder module. First MB, Williams JBW, Benjamin LS, Spitzer RL: Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 Personality Disorders (SCID-5-PD). Arlington, VA, *American Psychiatric Association*, 2016

Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) (Screening)

The Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) is an unstructured interview used to determine social and occupational functioning. All ratings are focused on functioning independent of the overall severity of psychological symptoms. Ratings are provided for four different timepoints: 1) premorbid level, 2) level twelve months ago, 3) current score in the past month, and 4) lowest score in the past year. Goldman, H. H., Skodol, A. E., & Lave, T. R. (1992). Revising axis V for DSM-IV: a review of measures of social functioning. *Am J Psychiatry*, 149, 9.

Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) (Follow-up)

The Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale (SOFAS) is an unstructured interview used to determine social and occupational functioning. All ratings are focused on functioning independent of the overall severity of psychological symptoms. Ratings are provided for two different time points: 1) level twelve months ago, and 2) current score in the past month. Goldman, H. H., Skodol, A. E., & Lave, T. R. (1992). Revising axis V for DSM-IV: a review of measures of social functioning. *Am J Psychiatry*, 149, 9.

Sociodemographics

Within an unstructured interview, a wide range of socio-demographic information, such as the participant's age, sex, gender, ethnicity, and relevant information about the biological parents, is assessed to calculate socioeconomic status.

The Patient Global Impression Scale – Severity (PGI-S)

The Patient Global Impression Scale – Severity (PGI-S) is a single-item questionnaire utilized to assess the participants' impression of the severity of their illness in the past seven days. Yalcin, I., & Bump, R. C. (2003). Validation of two global impression questionnaires for incontinence. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 189(1), 98-101.

Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) (Screening)

If a participant reports during the screening having experienced a prior brain injury, the traumatic brain injury screening assessment is completed. Based on several questions the interviewer rates the severity of the injury.

FIGS Scoring Algorithm Changes

All changes apply equally to mother, father, sibling, and child variables throughout the instrument unless otherwise stated.

Formula Bug Fixes

Single quotes were removed from numeric values used in greater-than and less-than comparisons throughout the scoring algorithm (e.g., >='3' corrected to >=3). In REDCap, these quotes caused incorrect behavior when sum score variables were blank.

Depression Diagnostic Criteria

Criteria for possible depression were updated

dposs1: Functional impairment is no longer required as a criterion, as a formal history is considered sufficient evidence on its own. Previously both a history of diagnosis or treatment and functional impairment not scored as absent were required.

dposs2: Criteria were changed so that functional impairment scored as absent now excludes a possible depression diagnosis, whereas previously only missing functional impairment qualified. The updated criteria require functional impairment to be scored as either yes or unknown.

Depression Key Symptom (dkey)

The formula for dkey was updated to return 9 (missing) when both depressed mood (D01) and anhedonia (D02) are rated as unknown. Previously, cases where both core symptoms were unknown were returned as 0, meaning they were treated the same as cases where symptoms were confirmed absent. This affects downstream depression diagnosis variables for any participant where both D01 and D02 are unknown.

Depression Missing Data (dmiss)

Missing data variables for depression (dmiss1, dmiss2, dmiss3) were omitted and replaced with a single revised dmiss formula. The revised formula more accurately captures cases of insufficient information for a depression diagnosis.

Mania Missing Data (mmiss)

Missing data variables for mania (mmiss1, mmiss2, mmiss3) were omitted and replaced with a single consolidated mmiss formula. The revised formula more accurately captures cases of insufficient information.

Moodmiss Variable

The moodmiss variable, which flags cases with insufficient mood disorder information, was updated to also capture cases where one mood disorder is absent and the other is missing. Previously moodmiss only flagged cases where both depression (ddx) and mania (mdx) were coded as missing (9). This change affects nonaffective and affective psychosis diagnoses for cases in these scenarios.

Psychosis Criteria – P17 branching logic

Item P17 (mood-psychosis symptom overlap) now displays only when at least one depression or mania screening item was answered yes AND at least one psychosis screening question answered yes. Previously P17 appeared under broader conditions.

Psychosis Possible Diagnosis (pposs)

The formula for possible psychosis (pposs) was updated to add an explicit check on P12. Previously P12 was not included in the pposs formula. The updated formula requires p12 to be either 1 (little or no reason to think caused by illness or drugs) or unknown (NA) for a possible diagnosis to be assigned.

Psychosis Missing Data (pmiss)

Missing data variables for psychosis (pmiss1, pmiss2, pmiss3) were omitted and replaced with a single revised pmiss formula. The original variables were noted as not comprehensively defining missing data. The revised formula defines missing psychosis data across three scenarios: when at least one key psychotic symptom (delusion, hallucination, or disorganized speech) is present but it is unknown whether it is attributable to a medical or drug-related cause and there is no confirmed history of diagnosis or treatment; when all key psychotic symptoms are unknown and

diagnosis or treatment is not confirmed; and when psychosis screening responses are unknown and none are endorsed.

Psychosis Sum Score (psum)

The psychosis symptom sum (psum) was updated to include only items P01–P09, representing key psychotic symptoms. Items P10 and P11 were removed as they capture disorganized behavior, which is not considered a key psychotic symptom for the purposes of this scoring algorithm.

Psychosis Domain Scoring (pdo1–pdo5)

Domain variables pdo1–pdo5 were revised to use a value of -1 to indicate insufficient information within a domain, replacing five separate domain-level missing indicator variables (pdo1miss–pdo5miss), which were omitted. The new -1 coding applies more consistent and stringent criteria, requiring that no items within a domain are scored as present and that a minimum number are scored as unknown before a domain is flagged as missing. Variables pdosum and pdomissingsum were updated to handle the -1 coding.

Nonaffective and Affective Psychosis Missing Data (napmiss and apmiss)

The napmiss variable was substantially revised and intermediate variables napmiss1 and napmiss2 were omitted. The original variables did not comprehensively define missing data, with missing cases being incorrectly coded as absent. The revised formula flags missing when any of the following conditions are met: psychosis status is unknown; mood disorder information is insufficient; mood-psychosis symptom overlap (P17) is unknown in the presence of any mood disorder diagnosis; or psychosis symptom domain information is incomplete (one domain present with one or more missing; no domains present with two or more missing; or all five domains missing).

The apmiss variable was separately updated. Previously apmiss flagged cases as missing when psychosis status was unknown, mood disorder information was insufficient, or mood-psychosis symptom overlap (P17) was unknown. The updated formula adds the same psychosis symptom domain conditions as the revised napmiss formula.

Nonaffective Psychosis Possible Diagnosis (naposs2)

The criteria for a possible nonaffective psychosis diagnosis were updated in relation to item P17, which captures whether mood symptoms overlap with psychotic symptoms. Previously, a possible nonaffective psychosis diagnosis could be assigned when P17 was either scored as indicating no mood-psychosis overlap or when P17 was unknown. The updated formula requires P17 to be explicitly scored as indicating no mood-psychosis overlap before a possible nonaffective psychosis diagnosis can be assigned, excluding cases where this information is unknown.

Affective Psychosis Criteria

The criteria for affective psychosis diagnoses were updated across all levels. For definite affective psychosis (dapdef/mapdef), the prior criteria required definite psychosis, definite

depression or mania, and a positive d12/m12 check. The final implemented criteria require definite psychosis and any level of mood disorder (possible, probable, or definite), with the d12/m12 check removed. For probable and possible affective psychosis (dapprob, mapprob, dapposs, mapposs), the prior criteria required a specific matching level of mood disorder, a positive d12/m12 check, and no explicit psychosis level check. The final implemented criteria require the psychosis diagnosis to meet the corresponding level of certainty, accept any level of mood disorder, and the d12/m12 check has been removed from these variables.

Diagnosis Variable Ordering

The evaluation order for all final diagnosis variables was standardized to: definite → probable → possible → missing → absent. Previously, missing was evaluated before definite, probable, or possible in some variables. The corrected order ensures that a missing code is only assigned when a case does not meet any diagnostic criteria and has insufficient information.

Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

Electroencephalography (EEG) Data

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **2228** unique participants, **1470** have both baseline and month_2 EEG visits, 728 have baseline only, and 30 have month_2 only.
- Six EEG sessions, all baseline, that were included in Release 3.0 have been excluded from Release 4.0. Two had their human-rated QC score degraded since Release 3.0, thus were not included. The src_subject_id values for these 2 are HA04486 and WU04908. One participant, ME51121, was excluded at the request of the Prescient network. The other three: CP87798, JE04581, ME01671 were left out of NDA4 due to a technical error that made their consent dates unavailable at the time of the data freeze.
- Month_2 followup sessions for participants that did not have a baseline visit are now included in release 4.0.

Selection criteria:

- Human-rated QC score of 2 or higher for raw data.
- For derived measures, sessions with a QC score of 3 or higher were automatically included, and those with a QC score of 2 were evaluated for inclusion independently for each measure.

Known Issues:

No known issues at this time.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia EEG Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for EEG Acquisition in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10472226>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
EEG raw data	eeg_sub_files01
EEG task-related derived measures	ampscz_eeg_featurestask01
EEG eyes open and closed rest derived measures	ampscz_eeg_featuresrest01

General Information:

64 channels of EEG data were acquired at 1000 Hz on a Brain Products system with two 32-channel actiCHamp modules. There were 5 different paradigm types:

- Combined Visual Oddball (VOD) with Mismatch Negativity (MMN)
- Auditory Oddball (AOD)
- Auditory Steady-State Response (ASSR)
- Resting-State w/ Eyes Open
- Resting-State w/ Eyes Closed

The VOD+MMN paradigm combined passive auditory MMN stimuli with a VOD task. The MMN stimuli occurred at 500 ms intervals and consisted of frequent (90%) Standard 633 Hz tones of 50 ms duration, interspersed with infrequent (10%) Deviant 1000 Hz tones of 100 ms duration. The VOD stimuli were a series of 496 ms duration Standard 4° diameter blue circles (80%) on a white background presented on a visual display 70 cm from the participant, with occasional Target 8° blue circles (10%), and random Novel full-screen fractal pattern images (10%). The task was to attend to the image sequence and press a button when the Target images appeared while not responding to the Standard or Novel images. The AOD paradigm was analogous to the VOD paradigm but with auditory instead of visual stimuli. Standard sounds were 1200 Hz tones of 50 ms duration. Target sounds were 500 Hz tones of 50 ms duration, and Novel sounds were short audio clips. Again, participants attended to the sound sequence and were instructed to press a button only following Target sounds. ASSR paradigm stimuli were a 40 Hz auditory click train of 500 ms duration repeated at 1.1 sec intervals. There was no active task for ASSR. Resting-state EEG was acquired with eyes open and closed for 3 minutes each. VOD+MMN and AOD paradigms had runs of roughly 4-5 minutes. There were 5 runs of VOD+MMN and 4 runs of AOD presented in alternating order, starting with VOD+MMN and followed by ASSR, eyes open rest, and eyes closed rest.

A QC dashboard was developed allowing lead investigators to preview analyses of all 5 paradigm types in each session if available, as well as various session-level quality measures such as electrical impedance at each electrode, bridging between electrodes, median line noise levels, and counts of stimulus event markers. The dashboard allowed each session to be given one of four ratings: 1 = no unusable data, 2 = some paradigms usable, 3 = all paradigms usable, 4 = all paradigms usable and excellent data quality.

Instrument Descriptions

Raw Data Description

Data files are in a zip file format, which contains the raw data in [BrainVision Core data format](#) with .vhdr, .vmrk, and .eeg extensions. Event markers in the Brain Vision .vmrk files are as follows.

- 'S 1' AOD Standard
- 'S 2' AOD Target
- 'S 4' AOD Novel
- 'S 5' AOD Response
- 'S 8' ASSR click train
- 'S 16' MMN Standard
- 'S 17' VOD Response
- 'S 18' MMN Deviant
- 'S 20' Resting w/ eyes open 1s interval
- 'S 24' Resting w/ eyes closed 1s interval
- 'S 32' VOD Standard
- 'S 64' VOD Target
- 'S128' VOD Novel

The file naming convention for zip files is a 2-character site code, followed by a 5-digit subject identifier number, followed by _eeg_visit, and a 1-digit visit number, which is either 1 for baseline or 2 for a 2-month followup, e.g. SF12345_eeg_visit1. Note that electrical line noise frequency will vary according to the geographic location of the site. Within the zip files, continuous segments of data have [EEG BIDS](#) format file names where the task labels are one of VODMMN, AOD, ASSR, RestEO (eyes open), or RestEC (eyes closed) and each continuous segment of data is given a separate run index. Note that run indices in the file names do not necessarily correspond to “runs” of data as described above. If the acquisition was paused during a run, its data will be spread over 2 or more sets of BrainVision files. Dates in the session labels of the file names have been shifted by standard AMP-SCZ offsets for each participant to protect identity.

Task-related Derived Measures

Average amplitudes of ERP difference waves over fixed time intervals are given at each of 64 channels for the MMN and oddball tasks. For the ASSR task, average changes in total power and evoked power relative to a baseline interval, as well as inter-trial coherence are given. For more precise descriptions see the data element descriptions in the [ampcsz_eeg_featurestask01](#) dictionary.

Resting State Derived Measures

Mean absolute power spectral density in 5 frequency bands for each of 64 channels is reported for both eyes open and eyes closed runs of 180 seconds of resting EEG. The frequency bands were defined as follows. See the [ampcsz_eeg_featuresrest01](#) dictionary for more information.

Delta	1 to 3 Hz
Theta	4 to 7 Hz
Alpha	8 to 12 Hz

Beta	13 to 30 Hz
Gamma	31 to 48 Hz

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) Data

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Data Release 4.0 includes scans from the baseline and follow-up MRI sessions. There are **2063** baseline sessions (CHR/CC: 1517/546) and **1419** follow-up sessions (CHR/CC: 1212/207).

Important note: At the current time, we discourage users from mixing data from Release 3 with Release 4 – i.e., merging data from “new” participants in Release 4 into already downloaded data from Release 3 is discouraged, since that would lead to a combined dataset of mixed provenance that is not appropriately described as either Release 3 or 4. At some point in the future, as bandwidth allows, we may conduct a detailed forensic comparison of Release 3 vs. 4, at which point we would be able to provide details on what precisely changed between Release 3 and 4 for participants/sessions in common between the two, at the level of individual files.

Change Log (vs. Release 3.0):

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **2088** unique participants with MRI data.
- Follow-up sessions are included even when the participant’s baseline session is missing or not part of this release.
- Scans deemed to be “unusable” or “low” quality are now included in a separate subdirectory named “series_with_quality_issues”. See the [Visual Quality Control](#) section for details.
- Scans with incidental findings of possible relevance are also now included. See the [Incidental Findings](#) section for details.
- **For both of the above reasons, users should give more thought and attention to which scans to include in their analyses when using Release 4.0 data, rather than simply using all the data provided.**
- FreeSurfer reconstructions generated using the longitudinal FreeSurfer stream were added in addition to those from the cross-sectional stream. SynthSeg outputs were also added to the reconstruction directories for each cross-sectional pipeline. See the [FreeSurfer](#) section for more details.
- Diffusion measures from a Tract-Based Spatial Statistics (TBSS) pipeline are NOT included in this release. See the [Diffusion Derived Measures](#) section for details.

- More details are provided regarding console software version changes and protocol deviations. See the “Events” column in the [Imaging Protocols](#) table and the [List of deviations](#) section.
- Excluded sessions:
 - Baseline sessions from JE04581, ME01671, and SL06259 were excluded from Release 4.0 due to dataflow-related issues.

Selection Criteria:

- The vast majority of potentially available MRI data has been provided in this release.
 - A small number of MRI scans are currently excluded due to data formatting and other technical considerations that require additional review. These cases are being addressed and should be available in the next release.
- Criteria for inclusion in this release were:
 - Participants with data transferred to the DPACC by 12/01/2025.
 - Sessions are included if they contain any usable imaging data, excluding those that contain only the spin-echo EPI scans (“fmap” scans).
 - Sessions with any **unexplained** deviations from the AMP SCZ MRI protocol (see protocol details below) or that need correction in the MRI Run Sheet by the site are excluded. Only two sessions were excluded due to unexplained deviations, which were caused by missing series descriptions or discrepancies in file counts.
 - If a given intended scan was repeated within a scan session, only the series with the better quality is included, as determined by the information provided in the MRI Run Sheet and a visual review of the scan quality.
 - All series, including those with visual quality control (QC) scores corresponding to “unusable” or “low” quality scans, are now included in a “series_with_quality_issues” folder under the session directories, for the following modalities: T1w, T2w, dMRI, and rs-fMRI. The quality score was assigned following criteria documented in the [Visual Quality Control](#) section below.
 - Participants with confirmed neurological findings as described in “[Incidental Findings](#)” section, are now included in the Release 4.0 data and the categories of each incidental finding are stated in the `comments_misc` field of the `image03` csv. (These were excluded from Release 3.0).
 - Note: The AMP SCZ MRI protocol includes alternative reconstructions for T1w and T2w scans on some of the platforms. As was the case for Release 3.0, Release 4.0 includes a [single reconstruction](#). The included reconstruction applies receive-field bias field intensity correction. On the Siemens and Philips platforms the provided reconstruction DOES NOT apply gradient nonlinearity correction (a.k.a., geometric distortion correction). However, the reconstruction provided for the GE platform includes the GE provided 3D correction referred to as ‘gradwarp’. Future releases may include additional reconstructions.
- **Inclusion criteria for FreeSurfer:**
 - FreeSurfer data is available **only** for sessions that include both T1w and T2w scans as described in the “[FreeSurfer](#)” section. Note that FreeSurfer was run

- regardless of the visual QC scores of the input T1w and T2w scans. The FreeSurfer outputs themselves have NOT been QC'ed or edited in any fashion.
- This represents 2080 subjects and 3466 sessions in total (2053 baseline and 1413 follow-up sessions; 1386 subjects having both).
 - The `qc_outcome` field in the `imagingcollection` csv is labeled as 'questionable' when either the T1w or T2w scan was rated as low/poor quality during [Visual Quality Control](#).
 - Among these, 1,374 subjects underwent processing with the FreeSurfer longitudinal stream. This includes:
 - 1,370 subjects with usable longitudinal "base" templates
 - 4 subjects with longitudinal templates that were subsequently identified as having been incorrectly generated, and whose FreeSurfer longitudinal stream results should not be used (noted in [Known Issues](#) section)
 - For these subjects:
 - Longitudinal stream baseline sessions: 1,359 total (1,355 usable, 4 that should be excluded, noted in [Known Issues](#))
 - Longitudinal stream follow-up sessions: 1,361 total (all usable).

Known Issues

- A list of subjects/sessions with protocol deviations is provided. (See the [List of deviations](#) section).
- FreeSurfer output WAS NOT QC'ed or manually edited.
- FreeSurfer reconstructions were run without optimization for high-resolution processing, and therefore do not fully leverage the sub-1 mm spatial resolution of the AMP-SCZ T1w and T2w images.
- Estimated intracranial volume (eTIV) derived from the default recon-all processing stream can be unreliable in some subjects due to failures in the affine Talairach transform (from which eTIV is solely estimated). For a more robust estimate of intracranial volume, it is strongly recommended to instead use the SynthSeg-derived total intracranial (volume).
- Exclude the longitudinal stream FreeSurfer outputs for the following subjects: **ME67845, ST43655, YA22164, YA25405, PV25103**.
 - For these subjects, an incorrect session was used to generate the longitudinal "base" template. Consequently, both the subject-specific template and all resulting timepoints from the longitudinal stream are invalid and should not be used in any analysis.
 - This exclusion applies to all datasets with the following `image_collection_desc` values for those 4 subjects:
 - "FreeSurfer longitudinal pipeline outputs for subject template creation step"
 - "FreeSurfer longitudinal pipeline outputs; Baseline"
 - "FreeSurfer longitudinal pipeline outputs; Followup"

- The following individuals have a longitudinal “base” template, but the listed FreeSurfer longitudinal stream timepoint processing failed, and thus is not available as part of Release 4:
 - **HK23127** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME65714** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **ME67089** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **ME67178** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **ME67467** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **ME69398** (Followup) [longitudinal Baseline timepoint available however]
 - **ME69493** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME70006** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME71050** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME71199** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME72626** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **ME75862** (Baseline, Followup)
 - **PV04769** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **SF61300** (Baseline) [longitudinal Followup timepoint available however]
 - **SI35347** (Baseline, Followup)

List of MRI-related Instruments (csv’s):

Instrument	Short Name
MRI unprocessed data	image03
FreeSurfer reconstructions	imagingcollection01

General Information

This document describes the MRI data included in the AMP SCZ Data Release 4.0. The AMP SCZ study collects up to two MRI sessions from each participant, a baseline and a follow-up session. The scan protocol includes scans consisting of structural T1- and T2-weighted (T1w and T2w) scans, three diffusion MRI scans (two b0 with ‘AP’ phase-encoding polarity and one multishell with ‘PA’ polarity), four resting state functional scans (rs-fMRI, two with AP and two with PA polarity), and three pairs of distortion maps (AP and PA polarity) for correction of distortions: one collected before the anatomical scans, one before the first block of rs-fMRI scans, and one before the second block of rs-fMRI scans.

Note that while the follow-up MRI session was assigned as a “Month 2” assessment within the AMP SCZ protocol, the actual interval between the baseline and follow-up MRI sessions can vary considerably across individuals, so be sure to consider this interval in analyses and when attempting to associate the MRI data with other types of data. Below are summary statistics for the time between baseline MRI data collection and the follow-up MRI (“Month 2”).

Summary of the number of days between baseline and follow-up MRI data collection

Mean	Median	SD	Minimum	Maximum
99 days	84 days	51 days	33 days	712 days

Detailed Information

Imaging Procedures

The scan sessions were collected by trained study personnel or imaging technologists familiar with the study and all relevant SOPs. Metal and health screening were performed before each session, following each imaging facility’s standards for patient screening and preparations (e.g., metal check, MRI screening forms, dress code, earplugs, squeeze ball, etc). During patient positioning, head coil padding was used as much as possible to create a snug but comfortable fit. Participants were instructed on the importance of remaining still in the magnet and were asked not to move their heads or bodies. Playing music or video clips was allowed during all scans except resting-state fMRI scans (rs-fMRI). During rs-fMRI scans, a fixation cross was displayed on the screen, and participants were instructed to focus their gaze on the crosshair. Participants were asked to blink naturally, relax their minds, maintain a steady breathing pattern, and remain still.

Imaging Protocols

The two capitalized alphabet letters in the participant ID represent the site code. See the table below. Please note the “Events” column in the table below, which documents software transitions and other major events occurring during the study that may affect consistency. **Please also carefully review the “[Lists of deviations](#)” section.** The software version information can be found in the sidecar ‘.json’ files that accompany the imaging NIFTIs. Note that the event dates listed in the table are real dates, whereas all session dates in the released data have been shifted by offsets (-14, -7, +7, or +14 days) to protect personally identifiable information (but with a consistent shift applied for all assessments within a given individual, so that all *intervals* between assessments remain correct and precise).

Institution Name	Site code	Scanner type	Network	Events
U. of Oregon	OR	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 from VE11E: 8/1/2023
Harvard (Beth Israel)	BI	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 from VE11E: 11/20/2023
Northwell	NL	Prisma	ProNET	
UNC	NC	Prisma	ProNET	Moved to a new Prisma scanner 6/1/2023. Note that the DeviceSerialNumber 67094 and 24d905581b269d7e represent the same machine (prior to the June 2023 switch). The post-June 2023 Prisma scanner has the DeviceSerialNumber of 8eabf48a99d5ec91. That scanner upgraded to XA30 from VE11E in the last week of Feb. 2025.
UCSD	SD	Prisma	ProNET	

Yale	YA	Prisma	ProNET	
UCSF/Mission Bay	SF	Prisma	ProNET	
Penn	PA	Prisma	ProNET	Scanner shut down for flooding 12/16/2022 - 1/5/2023
Pittsburgh (UPMC)	PI	Prisma	ProNET	
UC Irvine	IR	Prisma	ProNET	
Temple	TE	Prisma	ProNET	Scanner down due to cooling failure 12/15/2022 - 3/13/2023
Washington U (St. Louis)	WU	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 from VE11C: 3/16/2023
Montreal, CA	MT	Prisma	ProNET	Gradient coil replaced, 10/7/2024
Cambridge UK	CM	Prisma	ProNET	
Munich, Germany	MU	Prisma	ProNET	
Seoul, South Korea (SNU)	SL	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 from VE11C: 7/10/2023
Ohio State	OH	Prisma	ProNET	
Rochester	UR	Prisma	ProNET	
Columbia University	CU	Prisma	ProNET	
UCLA	LA	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 from VE11C: 4/21/2023
Northwestern	NN	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade to XA30 (with 12-bit recon) from VE11C: 12/5/2022; Upgrade to 16-bit recon (still XA30): 2/2/2023
Madrid, Spain	MA	Prisma	ProNET	
Mt. Sinai	SI	Prisma	ProNET	Upgrade from 12-bit recon on XA30 to 16-bit recon (still XA30): 2/17/2023. First 2 participants used a 32ch coil. The remaining participants used a 64ch coil.
Calgary, CA	CA	GE (MR750 & UHP)	ProNET	Upgrade from DV26/MR750 to MR30.1/UHP on 1/18/2024
Georgia	GA	GE (MR750)	ProNET	
King's College, UK	KC	GE (MR750)	ProNET	Scanner down 9/17 - 10/7/2024 due to the gradient amplifier needing replacement.
Hartford (Institute of Living)	HA	Skyra	ProNET	
Pavia, Italy	PV	Skyra	ProNET	Magnet quenched 10/23/2023; First scan after quench was 1/15/2024
Birmingham, UK	BM	Prisma	Prescient	
Singapore	SG	Prisma	Prescient	
Melbourne	ME	Prisma	Prescient	Upgrade to XA30 (12-bit recon) from VE11C: 12/9/2022; Upgrade to 16-bit recon (still XA30): 1/13/2023; Cracked gradient coil replaced in late Nov. 2023. The ME site started using a 2nd scanner (16-bit recon on XA30) on 12/1/2023.
Jena, DE	JE	Prisma	Prescient	Upgrade to XA60 from XA30 on 7/26/2024
Lausanne, CH	LS	Prisma	Prescient	
Cologne, DE	CG	Prisma	Prescient	Started study with 12-bit recon on XA30. Upgrade to 16-bit recon (still XA30) on 2/8/2024

Hong Kong	HK	Prisma	Prescient	
Copenhagen, DK	CP	Philips (Achieva)	Prescient	
Adelaide	AD	Skyra	Prescient	
Gwangju, KR	GW	Vida	Prescient	Transition to XA50 from XA31 in Nov 2023.

For a comprehensive list of parameters for each scan, please refer to the BIDS sidecar JSON files accompanying the NIFTI files. However, you can find a summary of the MRI protocol for each scanner type in the table below. It's important to note that the “dMRI B0” scans include one diffusion weighted volume at the end of the scan, along with the preceding B0 volumes. To obtain the specific diffusion weighting and direction for each volume, please consult the corresponding ‘.bval’ and ‘.bvec’ text files. Not shown in this table are the spin-echo EPI (“distortion map”) scans acquired with the same resolution and echo-spacing as the rs-fMRI scans, for use in ‘TOPUP’ style correction of susceptibility distortion.

Lists of deviations

Subjects with inconsistent software versions across sessions

Some scanners received software version upgrades over the course of the study. While sites attempted to maintain software version consistency between baseline and follow-up sessions for each participant, this was not always possible. The potential impact of the transition between software versions has not yet been established. We are sharing these cases in this release; however, please treat them with care, as software changes may cause subtle changes in the images and derived measures. The list of such cases and sessions is provided below:

ID	Baseline software version	Month 2 software version
BI05529	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
BI07622	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
CG02857	syngo MR XA30 12-bit	syngo MR XA30 16-bit
CG20994	syngo MR XA30 12-bit	syngo MR XA30 16-bit
CG72703	syngo MR XA30 12-bit	syngo MR XA30 16-bit
CG85336	syngo MR XA30 12-bit	syngo MR XA30 16-bit
GA35727	27\LX\MR Software release:DV26.0_R06_2132.a	30\LX\SIGNA_LX1.MR30.1_R04_2421.a
GA58464	27\LX\MR Software release:DV26.0_R06_2132.a	30\LX\SIGNA_LX1.MR30.1_R04_2421.a
GA60021	27\LX\MR Software release:DV26.0_R06_2132.a	30\LX\SIGNA_LX1.MR30.1_R04_2421.a
GA65259	27\LX\MR Software release:DV26.0_R06_2132.a	30\LX\SIGNA_LX1.MR30.1_R04_2421.a
GA65598	27\LX\MR Software release:DV26.0_R06_2132.a	30\LX\SIGNA_LX1.MR30.1_R04_2421.a
GW09340	syngo MR XA31	syngo MR XA50
GW67756	syngo MR XA31	syngo MR XA50
GW96256	syngo MR XA31	syngo MR XA50
IR21813	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
IR52749	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
IR53359	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
IR57361	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
JE16198	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE34479	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE48828	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE55524	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE99972	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE33564	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE56801	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
JE72889	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
LA15443	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30

LS28422	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
LS41703	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
LS64884	syngo MR XA30	syngo MR XA60
ME03013	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME00772	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME27132	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME54434	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME04934	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME19787	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME25689	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME33634	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME48643	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME67990	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME73814	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME81520	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
ME97666	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
NC21991	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
NC42496	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
OR10684	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
OR03049	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
OR10890	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
OR10973	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
OR11644	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU16193	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU17436	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU27051	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU36022	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU20875	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU24843	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30
WU45748	syngo MR E11	syngo MR XA30

Siemens sessions with 12-bit recons in their non-structural data

Here we list the Siemens sessions in which either the baseline or follow-up MR sessions used a 12-bit recon for the non-structural scans (i.e., the 'fmap', 'func', and 'dwi' EPI scans). This occurred because the earliest versions of the CMRR EPI sequences for the XA30 platform did not support the use of the "usual" 16-bit recon for those acquisitions. Absence of an entry indicates that the usual (16-bit) recon was used for that session. These scans were moved into the "series_with_quality_issues" folder under the session directories (see the [Visual Quality Control](#) section), out of an abundance of caution, but may be usable after review, for certain analyses. (The primary concern is the potential for quantization effects in the high b-value volumes of the dMRI scan, due to the reduced dynamic range available in 12-bit output relative to 16-bit output.)

ID	Baseline (12-bit)	Month 2 (12-bit)
CG02857	ses-20231129	
CG20994	ses-20231228	
CG37739	ses-20231113	ses-20240130
CG56125	ses-20240108	
CG58189	ses-20231227	
CG64142	ses-20231024	ses-20240116
CG71543	ses-20231205	
CG72703	ses-20231128	
CG80875	ses-20231205	
CG82334	ses-20231212	
CG85281	ses-20240130	
CG85336	ses-20231206	
CG97315	ses-20240408	
CG97854	ses-20240124	
MA33836	ses-20240604	
ME10086	ses-20221223	
ME50599	ses-20221230	ses-20230310
ME54434		ses-20230113
ME79913	ses-20221223	ses-20230217
ME93565	ses-20221230	ses-20230317
SI00726	ses-20230111	ses-20230428
SI03540	ses-20221214	ses-20230301
SI04099	ses-20230125	
SI05265	ses-20230215	ses-20230526
SL03607	ses-20230727	ses-20231004

Sessions with head coil deviations

Here we list a small number of sessions that used an atypical head coil for that site. These scans were also moved into the “series_with_quality_issues” folder under the session directories. It is suggested that they not be used in analyses.

ID	Session	Note
CA36377	ses-20240816	"48HAP" coil used instead of the standard Nova coil as used in other CA scans
CA00229	ses-20221205	"GE 32Ch" coil used instead of the standard Nova coil as used in other CA scans

Subjects with 3 total sessions

A small number of subjects had their MR data collected in 3 total imaging sessions, rather than 2. Here we explain what occurred in those 5 individuals.

ID	Sessions	Note
MA37432	Baseline: ses-20240625, ses-20240712	Baseline scan collected across different days: anatomical scans on ses-20240712, and dMRI and rs-fMRI collected on ses-20240625.
BI04369	Baseline: ses-20231222, ses-20240201	Baseline scan collected across different days: dMRI and rs-fMRI collected on ses-20231222, and anatomical scans on ses-20240201.
MA30973	Baseline: ses-20240705, ses-20240828	Baseline scan collected across different days: T2w anatomical scan collected on ses-20240828, and T1w, dMRI, and rs-fMRI collected on ses-20240705.
BI33542	Follow-up: ses-20240726, ses-20240830	Follow-up scan collected across different days: anatomical and first rs-fMRI collected on ses-20240726, and dMRI and second rs-fMRI collected on ses-20240830.
BI05529	Follow-up: ses-20231215, ses-20240201	Follow-up scan collected across different days: dMRI and rs-fMRI collected on ses-20231215, and anatomical scans collected on ses-20240201.

Deviation documentation within 'image03'

The 'comments_misc' field in 'image03' encodes information related to the following three items:

- (i) Non-structural scans with a 12-bit recon (rather than 16-bit) are indicated in the first item of the 'comments_misc' field.
- (ii) Deviations from the expected head coil at that site are indicated in the second item of the 'comments_misc' field
- (iii) Notes related to the incidental findings review (see below) are included in the third item of the 'comments_misc' field.

Visual Quality Control

Trained research assistants at the Data Processing and Coordination Center (DPACC) carefully examine the quality of the T1w, T2w, dMRI, and rs-fMRI scans by visual inspection. This visual QC process is crucial in identifying low-quality data. It complements other QC measures provided by automatic QC tools, which will be available in future releases. The DPACC visual QC scores are provided in the `qc_description` field of 'image03'. These scores were mapped to the `qc_outcome` field of 'image03' as noted in the table below.

- Single-band reference ('SRef'; in the 'func' BIDS directory) and spin-echo EPI volumes (for TOPUP-style estimation of susceptibility distortion; in the 'fmap' BIDS directory) were not visually inspected and are therefore labeled as 'undetermined' in the `qc_outcome` field.
- For the multi-volume dMRI and rs-fMRI data, all volumes were visually QC'ed.
- For scans with a `qc_outcome` value of **questionable** or **fail**, the corresponding reasons are recorded in the `qc_fail_quest_reason` field (more details below).
- Scans with a `qc_outcome` value of **questionable** or **fail** were moved into a "series_with_quality_issues" folder under the session directories (see example organization in the [Expected File Structure](#) section below).

Score (<code>qc_description</code> field)	Criteria	Corresponding <code>qc_outcome</code> value
1 Unusable data (Fail)	Severe motion, ringing, ghosting, or other artifacts	fail
2 Low/poor quality image, but possibly usable (Borderline Pass/Fail)	Moderately-severe motion, ringing, ghosting, or other artifacts	questionable
3 Good quality image, but with some issue(s) present (Pass)	Non-severe motion, ringing, ghosting, or other artifacts	pass
4 High quality image (Pass)	Virtually no motion, ringing, ghosting, or other artifacts	pass

QC Score breakdown by MR modality

MRI Modality	Score of 1	Score of 2	Score of 3	Score of 4
T1w	22 (0.6%)	63 (1.8%)	1270 (36.6%)	2119 (61.0%)
T2w	40 (1.2%)	79 (2.3%)	1094 (31.6%)	2246 (64.9%)
dMRI AP b0	35 (0.5%)	107 (1.6%)	1030 (15.3%)	5555 (82.6%)

dMRI PA	19 (0.6%)	127 (3.8%)	1436 (42.6%)	1786 (53.0%)
rs-fMRI PA	33 (0.5%)	97 (1.4%)	1188 (17.4%)	5498 (80.7%)
rs-fMRI AP	29 (0.4%)	88 (1.3%)	1082 (15.8%)	5641 (82.4%)

For scans with a `qc_outcome` value of **questionable** or **fail**, our internal (free-form) notes describing image quality issues were organized into the following set of predefined categories using a large language model (GPT-4.1-mini) and provided in the `qc_fail_quest_reason` field to simplify their presentation and interpretation. Each entry can be assigned to up to two categories, separated by a semicolon. The code used for this categorization is publicly available in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/AMP-SCZ/llm-mr-qc-categorizer>

Category Name	Description
Acceptable / no significant issue	Image quality acceptable; no or only minimal artifacts, usable for analysis.
Motion artifact	Blur, ghosting, or other artifacts clearly due to patient motion.
Susceptibility / distortion / signal dropout	Susceptibility artifacts, distortion near sinuses/ears, local signal loss or dropout.
Low SNR / noise	Grainy, noisy, low signal-to-noise ratio, difficult to see anatomy.
Coverage / slice issues	Incomplete brain coverage, truncation, wrong field of view (FOV), missing slices.
Ghosting / aliasing / wrap-around	Ghosting not obviously motion-related, aliasing, wrap-around artifacts.
Hardware / sequence / reconstruction issues	RF spikes, coil issues, shading, severe inhomogeneity, reconstruction problems.
Non-brain / dental / implant effects	Artifacts mainly due to dental hardware, implants, braces, or other non-brain sources.
Ringling / Gibbs artifact	Oscillatory edge patterns (Gibbs ringing) due to Fourier truncation during reconstruction; repeating ripples near sharp boundaries.
Other / unclear	Comments that do not clearly fit predefined categories or are ambiguous/unclear.

Incidental Findings

Incidental findings (IFs) may be encountered at several steps in data acquisition, QC, and processing. When potential IFs were identified on MRI, the images were reviewed by a neuroradiologist. If the IFs were confirmed as brain aneurysms, tumors, or other findings of neurological importance, the research networks initiated further clinical investigation and notified the participants as needed. To date, we are aware of only five cases of IFs that warranted further clinical investigation, but whose data remained in the study.

Our internal notes on incidental findings were also organized into a set of predefined categories using a large language model (GPT-4.1-mini) and stored in the third item within the 'comments_misc' field of 'image03' (see [Deviation documentation within 'image03'](#)) to

simplify their presentation and interpretation. The code used for this categorization is publicly available in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/AMP-SCZ/ilm-mr-qc-categorizer>. Each session can be assigned up to two categories.

Category Name (n: number of sessions)	Description
Cystic or CSF lesions (<i>n</i> = 287)	Arachnoid cysts, pineal cysts, benign CSF-containing lesions (excluding sinus cysts).
Sinus and mastoid pathology (<i>n</i> = 338)	Sinus mucosal thickening, maxillary sinus cysts, mucous retention cysts, sinusitis, mastoid effusion, sinus polyps.
White matter lesions (<i>n</i> = 23)	White matter hyperintensities, demyelination, chronic microvascular ischemic changes, perivascular leukomalacias.
Vascular abnormalities (<i>n</i> = 4)	Aneurysms, vascular malformations, venous anomalies, stenosis.
Masses / tumors (<i>n</i> = 10)	Neoplasms, growths, other mass lesions.
Anatomical variants, developmental anomalies (<i>n</i> = 117)	Cavum velum interpositum, ventricular asymmetries, heterotopias, leukomalacias.
Extracranial or skull findings (<i>n</i> = 4)	Scalp lesions, calvarial lesions, skull base abnormalities.
Other / nonspecific / normal variants (<i>n</i> = 291)	Non-specific, trivial, or normal variants not clearly classified above (including perceived cortical atrophy or enlarged ventricles).

Expected File Structure

The MRI data for all participants are organized and provided in BIDS format, adhering to the BIDS structure. In this format, the subject label is derived from the AMP SCZ IDs, while the session label corresponds to the scan date (adjusted by up to +/- one week, like all other dates). The data is organized into sub-directories as follows:

1. The 'anat' sub-directory contains T1w and T2w NIFTI files, along with their corresponding BIDS sidecar JSON files.
2. The 'dwi' sub-directory contains the DWI scan, two B0 scans acquired with opposite phase-encoding polarity to the DWI scan, and corresponding '.bvec' and 'bval' files (in FSL format). For Siemens, the single-band reference ("SBRef") data acquired at the beginning of the scan are included. These do not exist for the GE and Philips protocol (although the SBRef data is typically not used in processing dMRI data anyway).
3. The 'func' sub-directory contains two blocks of AP and PA resting-state fMRI data, including the "SBRef" data, which is used in some processing pipelines as a registration target for motion correction. "Ref" scans analogous to the Siemens "SBRef" exist for the rs-fMRI scans collected with the GE and Philips protocols..
4. The 'fmap' sub-directory contains spin-echo EPI scans acquired with AP and PA polarity for use with 'TOPUP' style estimation of the B1 field for distortion correction. Three such "field map" pairs were acquired in a typical session – one pair prior to the anatomical block, one pair prior to the first rs-fMRI block, and a third pair prior to the second rs-fMRI block. To facilitate the mapping of the field map pairs to the intended anatomical and fMRI scans, the JSON files of each field map include an "IntendedFor" flag. For

example, the file 'fmap/sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-1_epi.json' will contain a field indicating that the field map is intended for the anatomical scans.

5. When present for a given session, the “series_with_quality_issues” folder (new to Release 4.0) contains data requiring additional review – i.e., series with low/questionable or unusable visual QC scores, 12-bit data, or coil deviations.

```
{ "IntendedFor":  
  [  
    "bids::sub-AB01234/ses-20230601/anat/sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T1w.nii.gz",  
    "bids::sub-AB01234/ses-20230601/anat/sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T2w.nii.gz"  
  ]  
}
```

The file names follow specific patterns to provide relevant information:

1. The 'run' labels in file names indicate the order of series. For instance:
 - 'sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_dwi' represents the first b0 scan acquired.
 - 'sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_dwi' represents the second b0 scan acquired.
2. In the DWI file names, the number of shells indicates the type of diffusion protocol used:
 - 'acq-5shell' represents a DWI protocol with five diffusion weighting shells (i.e., “Tier 2” dMRI protocol).
 - 'acq-6shell' represents a DWI protocol with six diffusion weighting shells (i.e., “Tier 1” dMRI protocol, collected on a Prisma).

Example structure of one session

```
rawdata/  
├── sub-AB01234  
│   └── ses-20230601  
│       ├── series_with_quality_issues  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_dwi.bval  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_dwi.bvec  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_dwi.json  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_dwi.nii.gz  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-2_bold.json  
│       │   └── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-2_bold.nii.gz  
│       ├── anat  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T1w.json  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T1w.nii.gz  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T2w.json  
│       │   └── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_T2w.nii.gz  
│       ├── dwi  
│       │   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_sbref.json  
│       │   └── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-1_sbref.nii.gz
```

```

├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_dwi.bval
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_dwi.bvec
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_dwi.json
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_dwi.nii.gz
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_sbref.json
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-6shell_dir-PA_sbref.nii.gz
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_sbref.json
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_sbref.nii.gz
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_dwi.bval
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_dwi.bvec
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_dwi.json
├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_acq-b0_dir-AP_run-2_dwi.nii.gz
├── func
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-1_sbref.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-1_sbref.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-1_bold.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-1_bold.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-1_sbref.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-1_sbref.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-1_bold.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-1_bold.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-2_sbref.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-AP_run-2_sbref.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-2_sbref.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-2_sbref.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-2_bold.json
│   └── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_task-rest_dir-PA_run-2_bold.nii.gz
├── fmap
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-1_epi.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-1_epi.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-1_epi.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-1_epi.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-2_epi.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-2_epi.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-2_epi.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-2_epi.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-3_epi.json
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-AP_run-3_epi.nii.gz
│   ├── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-3_epi.json
│   └── sub-AB01234_ses-20230601_dir-PA_run-3_epi.nii.gz

```

FreeSurfer

FreeSurfer reconstruction has been performed using the official FreeSurfer Version 7.4.1 container from docker hub ([sha256:10b646](https://github.com/FreeSurfer/FreeSurfer)). T2w images were also provided to the recon-all command in addition to T1w images to improve pial surface placement. Thus, only the subset of

sessions with both T1w and T2w scans contain FreeSurfer data in this release (2080 subjects, 3466 sessions in total).

Note that in the `imagingcollection` csv, the `qc_outcome` field does NOT correspond to the quality of the FreeSurfer surfaces and segmentation (which was not reviewed), but rather the lower of the quality-rating of the input T1w and T2w images.

The recon-all commands used were:

Cross-sectional stream:

```
recon-all -subject <sessionID> -i <t1w> -T2 <t2w> -T2pial -all
```

Longitudinal stream, create “base” template:

```
recon-all -base <templateID> -tp <tp1> -tp <tp2> -all
```

Longitudinal stream, generate longitudinal timepoints:

```
recon-all -long <tp1> <templateID> -all
```

```
recon-all -long <tp2> <templateID> -all
```

Note that in Release 4, we did NOT run the longitudinal stream on “singleton” sessions for subjects that only had a single timepoint available. However, running the longitudinal stream on singleton sessions is in fact the approach recommended by FreeSurfer for the inclusion of such timepoints into analyses of the longitudinal stream data that conceptually would support the inclusion of single time points (such as linear mixed effect [LME] models, which can accommodate missing timepoints), so as to ensure that the singleton timepoints receive the same overall longitudinal stream processing (thus avoiding the possible introduction of biases due to mixing of cross-sectional and longitudinal stream processed data). We intend to do this as part of the next Release. In the meantime, users should NOT mix the cross-sectional data of the singleton sessions into the existing longitudinal stream processing.

The SynthSeg command was run from a containerized FS7.4.1, same as recon-all:

```
mri_synthseg --i <orig.mgz> --o <seg.mgz> \ --robust --cpu --vol  
<volumes.csv> --qc <qc.csv>
```

Diffusion Derived Measures

In Release 3.0, diffusion-derived measures were not harmonized for site or scanner platform differences, which can be appreciable in dMRI data. We strongly recommend that researchers wait for Release 5.0 before using diffusion-derived measures, as it will include harmonized diffusion data. For this reason, diffusion-derived measures have not been included in Release 4.0.

Digital Biomarkers: Actigraphy Data

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **916** unique participants.
- Wristband actigraphy data is included for all participants with available data, including those with poor quality due to missingness.
- Derived measures of sleep time, sleep quality and daily activity have been released. These measures were processed using the following software:
 - **DPSleep**: Deep Phenotyping of Sleep Open Source pipeline [1] analyzes the raw accelerometer data and extracts sleep and activity parameters using minute-based activity levels.

Selection criteria:

- Data for participants with up to 150 days from their onboarding date have been included in this release. The onboarding date refers specifically to the onboarding interview for the digital biomarker actigraphy study and is distinct from the consent date.
- Participants who had any data prior to October 31, 2025, are included in this release.

Known Issues:

No known issues at this time.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Digital Health Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for Actigraphy Acquisition in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10475887>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
Raw Accelerometer	actirec01
Sleep and Activity Derived Measures	device01

General Information

Raw Accelerometer Data:

This document provides an overview of the AMP-SCZ actigraphy data obtained from the actigraphy watch which includes raw accelerometer data and extracted sleep and activity parameters. The actigraphy watch used for data collection is the Axivity Ax3 (available at: <https://axivity.com/userguides/ax3/>). Participants receive the watch through the mail for each online digital biomarker check-in session and are instructed to wear it continuously for one month. Afterwards, they return the watch and wear a formatted fully-charged watch mailed to their address.

Derived Sleep and Activity Parameters:

DPSleep pipeline [1] is used to extract activity and sleep parameters. That includes:

1) a) Minute-based activity scores: Activity levels are calculated for each minute and they are categorized based on the individual's percentile of activity. Then scores are assigned to each minute between 1 to 5 based on the percentile thresholds of 10, 25, 50, and 75. When there is no data the minute is assigned at 0. b) Minute-based sleep scores: DPSleep pipeline then uses the activity scores to estimate the sleep epoch as the longest episode of low activity during the day. Minutes during the sleep epoch are assigned as 1 and the rest of the minutes are 0.

2) Daily sleep and activity parameters: The daily report of the DPSleep contains the following parameters:

study day, weekday, sleep onset from 6pm (hrs), wake time from 6pm (hrs), sleep duration (hrs), off wrist (mins), sleep immobility (%), wake activity (%), sleep fragmentation (%), raw wake activity, raw sleep activity, data availability.

For the data release in January 2025, the raw accelerometer data will be available for the first five available sessions of participants who have completed onboarding and returned their watch by October 31, 2025.

Key Points:

- Participants enrolled in watch actigraphy data for the digital biomarker are included if any data point is available for them during the first 60 days after onboarding.
- Data is captured for approximately 60 days of continuous wear.
- The raw data is stored in the parquet format to save space for large files. Apache Parquet is an open-source, column-oriented data file format designed for efficient data storage and retrieval. It provides efficient data compression and encoding schemes with enhanced performance to handle complex data in bulk [1].
- The file name indicates the recording period on the device, including the dates and times.

Instrument Descriptions

Raw Accelerometer Data Descriptions

Timestamps: The timestamps are in JAVA Time format, which represents the date and time converted into milliseconds. The nominal sampling rate is 12.5 Hz, but the sampling frequency may vary. Therefore, resampling is required for data analysis.

Accelerometer: The triaxial accelerometer measures acceleration in g (earth gravity, 9.8 m/s²). The three axes, Ax1, Ax2, and Ax3, correspond to the device's coordinate plane.

Derived Sleep and Activity Parameters Descriptions

Minute-based activity scores: Activity levels are calculated for each minute and they are categorized based on the individual's percentile of activity. Then scores are assigned to each minute between 1 to 5 based on the percentile thresholds of 10, 25, 50, 75. When there is no data the minute is assigned at 0. These activity scores are shown in the following files:

As a vector in:

`/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_scores+sleep_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.csv`

As a 1440xdays matrix in:

`/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_scores_6pmtto6pm_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.csv`

As a color-coded plot in:

`/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_scores_6pmtto6pm_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.eps`

An example is demonstrated here; where 0 to 5 is color-coded as white, blue, cyan, green, orange and red.

Minute-based sleep scores: DPSleep pipeline then uses the activity scores to estimate the sleep epoch as the longest episode of low activity during the day. Minutes during the sleep epoch are assigned as 1 and the rest of the minutes are 0. These sleep scores are shown in the following files:

As a vector in:

`/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_scores+sleep_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.csv`

As a 1440xdays matrix in:

`/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_sleep_6pmtto6pm_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.csv`

As a color-coded plot in:

/[study]-[subject]-actigraphy_sleep_6pmtto6pm_startDate-to-endDate_day26to85.eps

An example is demonstrated here; where blue is sleep.

Daily sleep and activity parameters:

The daily [day is defined from 6pm of previous calendar day to 6pm of today] report of the DPSleep contains the following parameters:

study day: relative day to the consent date. Consent is day 1.

weekday: days of the week. Monday is 1 and Sunday is 7.

sleep onset from 6pm (hrs): Hours from 6pm of the previous day. 12 AM is 6.

wake time from 6pm (hrs): Hours from 6pm of the previous day. 6 AM is 12.

sleep duration (hrs): Duration of sleep epoch from sleep onset to wake time.

off wrist (mins): Number of minutes the participant was not wearing the watch during the day.

sleep immobility (%): 100% minus average activity percent during sleep epoch.

wake activity (%): Average activity percent during wake epoch of the day [day's wake time till next day's sleep onset]

sleep fragmentation (%): Sleep fragmentation is calculated based on the formula for the fragmentation index defined in FDA approved Actiwatch user manual [3].

raw wake activity: The average raw activity during the wake epoch of the day is calculated based on the area under the curve of the frequency spectrum of the accelerometer along three axes.

raw sleep activity: The average raw activity during the sleep epoch is calculated based on the area under the curve of the frequency spectrum of the accelerometer along three axes.

data availability (0/1): Availability of the data to calculate sleep epoch parameters.

[1] <https://github.com/dptools/dpsleep>

[2] <https://parquet.apache.org/>

[3] https://www.camntech.com/Products/Legacy/Actiwatch_User.pdf

Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

Digital Biomarkers: Smartphone Data

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **1,603** unique participants with daily smartphone data and **1,145** participants with smartphone sensor data.
- A subset of PRESCIENT MindLAMP sensor data has been recovered through December 31, 2024.

Selection criteria:

- Data for participants with up to 150 days from their onboarding date has been included in this release. The onboarding date refers specifically to the onboarding interview for the digital biomarker smartphone study and is distinct from the consent date.
- Participants who had not reached 150 days post-onboarding by the network-specific cutoff dates were excluded from this release: PRONET (October 31, 2025) and PRESCIENT (December 31, 2024) (see Known Issues below for details regarding differing cutoff dates across networks).

Known Issues:

- In August 2023, the PRESCIENT MindLAMP server encountered technical issues affecting data transfer to the NDA database. Data collection continued with minimal interruption, and all data have been preserved on the PRESCIENT MindLAMP server. Efforts to export PRESCIENT phone sensor data from the server are ongoing. Due to this, the current release includes data only for participants who reached 150 day post-onboarding by December 31, 2024. Passive sensor data collected from January 2025 onward will be incorporated into future releases as data export and processing are completed. Of note, phone survey data collected via MindLAMP were not affected by this issue and remain up to date.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Digital Health Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for Digital Health - EMA and PS - Acquisition in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10475903>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
Geolocation	ampscz_sp_sensors01 , data_modality=geolocation
Accelerometer	ampscz_sp_sensors01 , data_modality=accelerometer
Screen state	ampscz_sp_sensors01 , data_modality=screen
Smartphone Survey	ampscz_sp_survey01
Phone Sensor Derived Measures	device01

General Information: Smartphone Survey and Smartphone Passive Sensor

This document describes the contents of the AMP-SCZ smartphone-based digital phenotyping study, which includes brief daily self-report surveys and passive data (geolocation, accelerometer, and screen state) collected via the MindLAMP app (<https://docs.lamp.digital>). Due to varying privacy preferences, participants could enroll in one of three study versions: (1) V1: all sensors enabled; (2) V2: all sensors enabled except geolocation; and (3) V3: no passive sensors (i.e., daily ambulatory surveys only).

Date and Time

All timestamps (date and time) are in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). To convert timestamps to local time, the regional time zone of the data collection site and daylight saving time must be accounted for.

File Format

Raw sensor data (geolocation, accelerometer, and screen state) is stored in Apache Parquet format. Apache Parquet is an open-source, column-oriented data file format designed for efficient data storage and retrieval. It provides efficient data compression and encoding schemes with enhanced performance for handling complex data in bulk [1]. In the Parquet files,

the "Relative_Time" field represents the number of days since the participant's consent date, where the consent date is defined as day 1.

Data Availability Metrics

- **GPS:** The "Available GPS (hrs)" column in the daily GPS-derived measures CSV file (e.g., [site_ID]-[ampscz_ID]-phone_gps_daily_*-to-*_day*to*.csv) represents the total hours of GPS data available for a given day.
- **Accelerometer:** The "Phone Accel Availability (hrs)" and "Phone Accel Availability (mins)" columns in the daily accelerometer-derived measures CSV file (e.g., [site_ID]-[ampscz_ID]-phone_accelerometer_daily_-to-_dayto.csv) represent the total hours or minutes of data available for a given day.
- **Screen state:** Screen state does not have a quality metric. It is recorded based on on/off events of the screen rather than a consistent sampling rate.
- The dates in the file name represent the date range of the phone data included, using **shifted dates**. To preserve participant privacy while maintaining the relative timing of events, a random number of days has been added to or subtracted from each participant's actual dates (i.e., shifted dates). Additionally, the "Relative_Time" field reflects the number of days elapsed since the consent date, also based on shifted dates.

Instrument Descriptions

Smartphone Sensor Data Descriptions

Geolocation

The location sensor records the device's current geospatial coordinates. Depending on the device operating system and device battery level, the source of the data from this sensor may alternate between GPS antennae (high accuracy), cellular tower triangulation (moderate accuracy), WiFi triangulation (poor accuracy), or a combination of these.

Note that raw geolocation data is not available in the general permission group (C3705 – "NIMH Data Archive"), and requires additional IRB approval for access (C4366 - "Personal Tracking Device").

Accelerometer

The triaxial accelerometer measures acceleration applied to the device. Each measurement is measured in Gs and is taken relative to the coordinate plane of the device, screen facing upwards. For example, a device resting face-up on a flat surface will report a measurement with the coordinate values <0, 0, 1>.

Screen

This sensor measure records when the screen was turned on or off, and when the device was locked or unlocked. This sensor **DOES NOT** record the time spent within specific apps or how many notifications were received.

Smartphone Survey Data Descriptions

30-item survey was offered once per day across the entire study. The mindLAMP app prompted a reminder of the survey every evening at 8 pm (local time) via the smartphone notification function. Participants recorded their responses based on the 7-point Likert scale via a draggable slider to select one option from a numerical range (see screenshot). The same 30-item questionnaire was provided in the order listed below:

Survey Questions in Order

The screenshot shows a mobile app interface for a 'Daily Survey'. At the top, there is a back arrow and the title 'Daily Survey'. Below that, it says 'Question 1 of 31'. The question is 'Today I felt cheerful.' with a note '1 being not at all, 7 being very much'. A horizontal slider with numbers 1 through 7 is shown, with a green circle indicating the selected response at 4. Below the slider, it says 'Your response: Moderately'. At the bottom, there is a green 'Next' button.

1. Today I felt cheerful.
2. Today I felt stressed.
3. Today I felt down.
4. Today I felt strange.
5. Today I felt content.
6. Today I felt suspicious of others.
7. Today I felt relaxed.

8. Today my thoughts were racing.
9. Today I felt enthusiastic.
10. Today I heard things that others couldn't hear.
11. Today I felt empty.
12. Today I felt anxious.
13. Today I could concentrate well.
14. Today I felt irritable.
15. Today I felt worried.
16. Today I could enjoy nice things when they happened.
17. Today I felt that others could read my mind.
18. Today I felt lonely.
19. Today I felt very special.
20. Today I felt energetic.
21. Today I felt that others could control me.
22. Today I felt motivated.
23. Today I felt like my thoughts were confused or blocked.
24. Today I saw things that others couldn't see.
25. Today I could handle what came my way.
26. Today I was able to function well.
27. Today I spent time with other people (live).
28. Today I spent time with other people (online/digitally).
29. Today I experienced a negative/unpleasant event.
30. Today I experienced a positive/pleasant event.

Passive Sensor Derived Measures Data Dictionary

For derived measures in NDA 4.0, we recommend using daily-level measures for GPS, accelerometer, and screen state data. Minute-level measures are also available but remain under development and will be validated in future releases. The filename format for daily measures is as follows:

Accelerometer: [site_ID]-[ampscz_ID]-phone_accelerometer_daily_[date_range]_day*to*.csv

GPS: [site_ID]-[ampscz_ID]-phone_gps_daily_[dates_range]_day*to*.csv

Screen State: [site_ID]-[ampscz_ID]-phone_screen_daily_[date_range]_day*to*.csv

Variable Name	Data Modality	Software	Description
Study_day			The number of days since the consent date, with the day of consent counted as <i>Day 1</i> .
Weekday			The day of the week, where 1 represents Monday and 7 represents Sunday.
Available GPS (hrs)	GPS	DPLocate	Phone GPS data availability during the day (h)

Distance from Home (km)	GPS	DPLocate	Largest daily distance from Home (The most visited place during the study is Home) (Km)
Radius of Mobility (km)	GPS	DPLocate	Radius of the smallest circle that includes all locations visited in a day (Km)
Percent Home (%)	GPS	DPLocate	Percentage of time spent at Home during the day (%)
Percent Home-Interpolated (%)	GPS	DPLocate	Percentage of time not spent in other than Home locations (%). The assumption is the missing GPS signal is always Home.
Number of Places	GPS	DPLocate	Number of different Points of Interest (POIs) visited during the day (#). Density Based Spatial Clustering is used to detect the POIs.
Distance Traveled (km)	GPS	DPLocate	Sum of distances traveled among different POIs during the day (Km)
Entropy	GPS	DPLocate	Information theoretical entropy (Shannon, 1997), which measured how participant's time was distributed over different POIs during the day.
Phone Accel Availability (0/1)	Accel	DPPhone	Availability of the data to calculate activity scores
Phone Accel Availability (mins)	Accel	DPPhone	Number of minutes during the day any accelerometer signal is available (mins)
Phone Accel Availability (hrs)	Accel	DPPhone	Number of hours during the day any accelerometer signal is available (h)
Phone Accel Score (0-6, 0=NA; Daily)	Accel	DPPhone	Daily minutes are scored based on (10, 25, 50, 75, 90) percentile thresholds of the phone acceleration activity from 1 to 6 and then averaged across the 1440 minutes of the day.
Phone Accel Scores (0-3; 0=NA; Minute)	Accel	PPhone	0 indicates not applicable (NA); 1 indicates a value below 75%; 2 indicates a value between 75% and 90% (exclusive); and 3 indicates a value above 90%.
Active Accel (mins)	Accel	DPPhone	Number of minutes during the day that their phone accelerometer-based activity is larger than 75 percentile.
Phone Screen Use (mins)	Screen State	DPPhone	Number of minutes during the day that the phone was in use (screen on) (mins)
Phone Screen Use (hrs)	Screen State	DPPhone	Number of hours per day with at least one minute of screen use.

[1] <https://parquet.apache.org/>

[2] Rahimi-Eichi, H., Coombs, G., Onnela, J.P., Baker, J. T. & Buckner, R. L. Measures of Behavior and Life Dynamics from Commonly Available GPS Data (DPLocate): Algorithm Development and Validation. *medRxiv* 2022.07.05.22277276 (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.07.05.22277276.

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Language Sampling

Release: 4.0, May 2026. **DOI:** [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Open-ended interviews are now included for 1,561 individuals at baseline and 1,112 individuals at month 2.
- PSYCHS interviews are now included for 1,106 individuals at screening, 726 at baseline, 663 at month 1, 752 at month 2, and 604 at month 3.
- Daily diaries have been added. The dataset now includes 36,465 diary entries from 892 individuals.
- Derived features are now included for 1,771 individuals (participants and interviewers) from open-ended interviews.
- Derived features are now included for 1,728 individuals (participants and interviewers) from PSYCHS interviews.
- Derived features are now included for 891 individuals (participants and interviewers) from audio diaries.
- Speaker roles are now specified as “participant” and “interviewer.”
- Average word frequencies are now based on the SUBTLEX-US corpus and reported in log-transformed form.
- A new pipeline has been created to generate the derived measures

Redaction of PII/PHI

- Human editors at TranscribeMe carefully review transcripts for protected health information (PHI) and personally identifiable information (PII). This includes names, geographic information more specific than a state, dates directly related to individuals, contact information, and other unique identifying numbers (see the Supplemental Materials for the PII/PHI redaction guidelines used in this project). Redacted material is initially marked with curly brackets and later replaced with the word “REDACTED.” To avoid introducing inconsistencies or artifacts into the dataset, redacted content is not replaced with descriptive placeholders (e.g., replacing “Atlanta” with {CITY} or with another city such as {CHICAGO}), because such substitutions could distort measures of interest, including vagueness, concreteness, and conceptual coherence.

Derived measures descriptions:

- Derived features are extracted from three kinds of speech samples: Open-ended interviews, PSYCHS interviews, and Daily Diaries. Verbatim transcripts were obtained for all speech samples using TranscribeMe, professional human transcriber service.

- The language data dictionary comprises 8 speech fluency and verbosity features ([Liebenthal et al. 2023](#)) and a set of 102 linguistic features that capture the most commonly observed grammatical and lexical features produced in conversational language. The linguistic features are organized into three categories—morpho-syntactic properties, parts of speech, and grammatical dependencies—with definitions and examples provided for each ([Bilgrami, Z. R., Castro, E., Agurto, C., et al., 2025](#)). Morphological features describe grammatical attributes such as person (first, second, third), definiteness, gender, tense (e.g., past), and number (e.g., plural). The parts-of-speech category includes word classes such as adjectives, adpositions, adverbs, determiners, nouns, pronouns, and verbs, using terminology from both the Universal Tagset and the Penn Treebank Tagset. Grammatical dependency features characterize syntactic relationships between sentence elements, including adjectival modification, coordinating conjunctions, discourse elements, interjections, subjects, direct and indirect objects, and open clausal complements. In addition to these linguistic features, derived measures include the total number of sentences per transcript and average word frequencies, computed separately for interviewers and interviewees.
- For all transcripts, language is first identified using the Stanza Python NLP library (version 1.11.0), with detected language codes cross-checked against the known languages spoken at each site to ensure accuracy. Metadata including research network code, subject ID, interview type, study day, session, and interview number are also prepared. Speaker roles (“participant” vs. “interviewer”) are assigned using OpenAI’s gpt-oss-120b model, served via vLLM (version 0.12.0) on NVIDIA hardware. All transcripts are then parsed with Stanza to extract morphosyntactic features. For English transcripts, average word frequency (reported in the word_freq column) is computed using log frequency values from the SUBTLEX-US corpus, which approximates spoken language (Brysbaert & New, 2009). Log frequency is defined as $\log_{10}(\text{FreqPM} + 1)$, where FreqPM denotes frequency per million words, reflecting the highly skewed distribution of word usage. Prior work shows that SUBTLEX-based frequencies better predict word processing and recognition times than frequencies derived from written corpora, likely due to their closer alignment with spoken language (Brysbaert et al., 2011; Dimitropoulou et al., 2010). Finally, to identify interviews potentially mislabeled as “PSYCHS” or “Open,” gpt-oss-120b is run again via vLLM to flag suspect files; these candidates are subsequently reviewed and corrected by two independent human reviewers before final label updates are applied.
- In addition, face features are derived from the video recording of each interview. The face features include confidence of face detection and facial action units, computed in OpenFace. The code for extracting these features can be found here: github.com/dptools/dpinterview.

Selection criteria:

- Data was drawn from transcripts produced prior to December 16, 2025.
- Mean volume over the entire transcribed interview must be at least 40 dB

Known Issues:

- There are no known issues.

Cognitive Measures

Release: 4.0, May 2026. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **2291** unique participants with baseline IQ measures and **2150** with baseline PennCNB measures.
- SVOLT follow-up sessions were corrected.
- SPLLT baseline and follow-up sessions with incorrect data were removed.

Selection criteria:

IQ assessments are checked to make sure that raw scores are properly converted to standardized scores. Participant age at the time of the assessment is estimated based on the interview date that was entered and the date that their demographic data was collected. This information is then used to recalculate their T-Scores and FSIQ scores from the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence (WASI) conversion tables. If these recalculated scores do not match what was entered by the raters, they are added to the QC trackers to be corrected. IQ data will only be uploaded **if it has no outstanding QC queries**.

All available PennCNB data is included.

Known-Issues for Release 4.0

In October 2024, the Penn CNB team uncovered a new issue with two Penn CNB tasks which are used in the AMP-SCZ project. The tests affected are the Short Penn List Learning Test (SPLLT) and Short Visual Object Learning test (SVOLT). The SVOLT was administered in two different forms (SVOLT-A and SVOLT-B). Baseline uses SVOLT-A while follow-ups use alternated forms. The Penn CNB team discovered that SVOLT-B scoring code was incorrect, however, this has now been corrected by the Penn CNB team, and scores have been fixed in the Penn Redcap, and corrections are reflected in this release. Regarding the SPLLT, a bug was discovered that caused incorrect logging of responses on some SPLLT versions deployed. **This bug affected a number of baseline sessions as well as a large number of early follow up sessions (contrary to a previous release that stated only follow-up versions were affected)**. Responses were recorded for only 8 of the 16 total words in the list for **these affected sessions**. **A file detailing the specific affected sessions was previously shared with the Cognition team. A fix for the affected SPLLT session data is currently being tested.** A fix was deployed by Penn CNB on 10/28 so that the SPLLT responses will be correctly

recorded from this date forward, however, for follow-up assessments before that date, the responses of 8 out of 16 items are not recoverable and therefore lost. **These affected data** have been removed from this release.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Cognition Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for Acquisition of Cognitive Measures in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10493862>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence II	wasi201
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale Fourth Edition [part 1]	wais_iv_part01
Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children V	wisc_v01
Short Penn List Learning	penncnb01
Motor Praxis	penncnb01
Short Penn Continuous Performance	penncnb01
Penn Emotion Recognition	penncnb01
Short Fractal N-Back	penncnb01
Digit-Symbol	penncnb01
Short Visual Object Learning	penncnb01

General Information:

This document describes the cognitive data included in the AMP-SCZ Data Release 4.0.

The AMP-SCZ study collects IQ assessment at two time points: baseline and 24 months. IQ was collected using one of the three following instruments: Wechsler Abbreviated Scale Intelligence II (WASI), Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale Fourth Edition (WAIS-IV), or the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children V (WISC).

For sites speaking languages other than English and where the WASI-II is not available in their language, the Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning subtests were administered from substitute Wechsler batteries (specifically, WISC-V for ages 12-15 and WAIS-IV for ages 16-30). While the item content and number may differ slightly from the WASI-II, the administration, recording, and

scoring of responses is exactly the same as described for the WASI-II. In terms of scoring, age-based standard scores for Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning will be a Scaled Score (rather than a T-score).

The Penn Computerized Neurocognitive Battery (PennCNB) is administered at multiple time points (baseline, week 8, week 26, week 52, week 104), and is being used to assess the cognitive domains most relevant to psychosis. There are 8 tests in the battery, and their order of administration is as follows:

Test Order	Test Acronym	Test Name	Length (mins)
1	SPLLT	Short Penn List Learning	3
2	MPRACT	Motor Praxis	2
3	SPCPTNL	Short Penn Continuous Performance	5
4	ER40	Penn Emotion Recognition	3.5
5	SFNB2	Short Fractal N-Back	10
6	DIGSYM	Digit-Symbol	3
7	SVOLT	Short Visual Object Learning	2.5
8	SCTAP	Short Computerized Finger-Tapping	3.5
Total			32.5

Instrument Descriptions:

Wechsler Abbreviated Scale Intelligence II (WASI-II)

The WASI-II two-subscale version is used. This includes the Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning subtests. Subtests are completed and scored per the manual's administration guidelines. For both subtests, total raw score is calculated by summing the item scores, including reversal items and un-administered items prior to the start point. Total raw scores are converted to T scores for each subtest using Table A.1 in the manual. T scores are corrected based on Test Age. T scores for Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning are then summed, and the Composite Score Conversion Table A.6 is used to derive the Full-Scale IQ-2 (FSIQ-2).

Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale Fourth Edition [part 1] (WAIS-IV)

The WAIS-IV Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning subtests are used. Subtests are completed and scored per the manual's administration guidelines. For both subtests, the total raw score is calculated by summing the correct item scores, including reversal items and un-administered items, prior to the start point. Total raw scores are converted to Scaled Scores for each subtest from the manual. To determine the Scaled Score, age-based scaled scores in the WAIS-IV manual were used. The average of the two scaled scores was added together and divided by 2.

For example, Vocab 12 + MR 10 = 22 / 2 Mean = 11. Full-scale IQ was estimated using the following online calculator: https://www.psychometrica.de/normwertrechner_en.html.

Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children V (WISC-V)

The WISC-V Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning subtests are used. Subtests are completed and scored per the manual's administration guidelines. For both subtests, the total raw score is calculated by summing the correct item scores, including reversal items and un-administered items, prior to the start point. Total raw scores are converted to Scaled Scores for each subtest from the manual. To determine the Scaled Score, age-based scaled scores in the WISC-V manual were used. The average of the two scaled scores was added together and divided by 2. For example, Vocab 12 + MR 10 = 22 / 2 Mean = 11. Full-scale IQ was estimated using the following online calculator: https://www.psychometrica.de/normwertrechner_en.html.

Short Penn List Learning Test

Test Title: SPLLT

Current Version: 2.00

Cognitive Domain Tested: Verbal Learning and Verbal Memory

Test Description: The PLLT is a measure of verbal learning and verbal memory. This test is modeled after the California Verbal Learning Test (CVLT) [1, 2, 3]. The original test is composed of immediate recall, short delay recall, short delay cued recall, long delay recall and long delay cued recall sessions (long delay recall = PLLTd). For the purposes of this study, the study was split to create 4 versions. Each version is administered at a different time point, with the exception of version "a", which is administered during both time points 1 and 5.

First, the participant will listen to a series of 16 words read to him/her by the test administrator. Each word falls within one of four semantic categories. The administrator follows the list of words in the computer screen as each word he/she must read is highlighted for 1 second (the exact time he/she can use to read each word). The administrator is the only person looking at the screen because the participant must not see any of the words read to him/her/her. Also, it is very important that the administrator read each word using a monotone voice so that no emphasis is given to any word in particular. After the participant listens to the words, he/she is asked to repeat as many of the items as he/she can remember in any order. This section comprises the immediate recall block, and it is repeated for a total of 3 consecutive blocks (both list reading and recall).

The test administrator marks the responses given by the participant by clicking with the mouse on each word the participant says on the computer. All words are displayed on the computer screen after the administrator finishes reading the prompts for each session. The administrator clicks on the words in the order the participant says. If the participant says a word that wasn't read to him/her/her or does not belong to the categories of the long delay cued recall blocks you are assessing, the administrator clicks on the "other" button.

There is a maximum of 25 total responses that may be given for the immediate recalls.

Rules & Variables: The SPLLT scores are based on the number of correct responses (excluding perseverations), number of perseverations, intrusions, semantic cluster, expected semantic cluster, chance-adjusted semantic clusters, serial clusters, expected serial clusters and chance-adjusted serial clusters for each block. The learning slope of blocks 1-5 (the immediate recall blocks) is given.

References:

- [1] Delis, D.C., Kramer, J.L., Kaplan, E. and Ober, B.A., 1987. California Verbal Memory Test: Manual. , Psychological Corporation, San Antonio, TX.
- [2] Delis, D.C., Kramer, J.H., Kaplan, E. and Ober, B.A., 1987. California Verbal Learning Test: Research Edition—Adult Version. , The Psychological Corporation, New York, NY.
- [3] Delis, D.C., Kramer, J. H., Kaplan, E., Ober, B. A., 2000. California Verbal Learning Test—2nd edition: Manual, The Psychological Corporation, San Antonio, TX.
- [4] Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Turner TH, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: I. Methodology and validation in healthy people. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):766-776.
- [5] Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: II. The Profile of Schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):777-788.

Motor Praxis Test

Test Title: MPraxis

Current Version: 2.06

Cognitive Domain Tested: Sensorimotor Ability

Test Description: The MPraxis is a measure of sensorimotor ability. It is also designed to familiarize the participant with the computer mouse used during nearly all of the WebCNP tasks. During the MPraxis, the participant needs to move the computer mouse cursor over an ever-shrinking green box and click on it once each time it appears on a different location on the test-page. If participants can't complete the MPraxis, it is likely they won't be able to complete any other WebCNP task.

Rules & Variables: The test is scored based on the number of correct responses for the test trials (Trial 2) and the median response times for the correct responses on the practice trial (Trial 1) and Trial 2.

Scoring Variable Notes: * The scores presented on WebCNP are raw scores. * All time-based scores (e.g. Response Time) are given in millisecond units (ms).

Reference:

Calkins ME, Ragland JD, Gur RE, Nimgaonkar LV, Pogue-Geile MF, Gur RC. Neurocognitive impairments reflect the degree of genetic predisposition to schizophrenia: evidence from a multiplex, multigenerational study. 2005; Poster Presentation.

Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Turner TH, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: I. Methodology and validation in healthy people. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):766-776.

Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: II. The Profile of Schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):777- 788.

Short Penn Continuous Performance Test-Number Version

Test Title: sPCPTn90

Current Version: 4.00

Cognitive Domain Tested: Visual Attention

Test Description: The sPCPTn90 is a measure of visual attention and vigilance based on the Penn CPT [1]. In this task, a series of red vertical and horizontal lines flash in a digital numeric frame (resembling a digital clock). The participant must press the spacebar whenever these lines form complete numbers. Each stimulus flashes for 300 milliseconds followed by a blank page displayed for 700 milliseconds, giving the participant 1 sec to respond to each trial. There are 90 trials in total, thus the actual test will take 90 seconds. A shortened practice trial will precede the actual test. Note: This version of the test is the Numbers Only version. The PCPT has both a numbers and a letters version, where in the latter part of the test, the participant must press the spacebar whenever the lines form a complete capital letter.

Rules & Variables: The sPCPTn90 is scored based on the number of true/false positives and true negative responses and their respective median response times.

Scoring Variables Notes: True Positives = spacebar press when the lines flashing form a complete number or a complete letter (a correct response). False Positives = spacebar press when the lines flashing do not form a complete number or a complete letter (an incorrect response). True Negatives = no spacebar press when the lines flashing do not form a complete number nor a complete letter (a correct response). the scores presented by the variables above.

Reference:

[1] Kurtz, M.M., Ragland, J.D., Bilker, W.B., Gur, R.C., Gur, R.E. (2001): Comparison of two forms of the continuous performance test, with and without working memory demands in healthy controls and patients with schizophrenia. *Schiz Res*, 48:307–316

[2] Gur, R.C., Ragland, J.D., Moberg, P.J., Turner, T.H., Bilker, W.B., Kohler, C., Siegel, S.J., Gur, R.E. (2001): Computerized neurocognitive scanning: I. Methodology and validation in healthy people. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 25:766–776

[3] Gur, R.C., Ragland, J.D., Moberg, P.J., Bilker, W.B., Kohler, C., Siegel, S.J., Gur, R.E. (2001): Computerized neurocognitive scanning: II. The Profile of Schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 25(5): 777-788.

Penn Emotion Recognition Task (k-ER40)

Test Title: k-ER40-d

Current Version: 3.60

Cognitive Domain Tested: Emotion Recognition

Test Description: The ER40 is a measure of emotion recognition. Participants are shown a series of 40 faces, one at a time, and asked to determine what emotion the face is showing for each trial. There are 5 answer choices: Happy, Sad, Angry, Fear and No Feeling. Participants respond to each trial by clicking with the mouse on the word describing the emotion each faces expresses. There are 4 female faces for each emotion (4 x 5 = 20) and 4 male faces for each emotion (4 x 5 = 20). Note: The faces are colored pictures taken, analyzed and rated as described in [1, 2, 3]. They derive from the University of Pennsylvania Emotion Recognition Task, 96 faces version, balanced for equality and intensity of emotion, age, gender and ethnicity [2].

Rules & Variables: The scores are based on the number of correct responses for female versus male faces; the number of correct happy, sad, angry, sad and no feeling faces; the number of false positives for happy, sad, angry, scared and no feeling faces; and the number of mild and intense emotion expressions correctly identified. Median response times are given for all categories.

Scoring Variable Notes: * The scores presented on WebCNP are raw scores. * All time-based scores (e.g. Response Time) are given in millisecond units (ms)

References:

[1] Gur RC, Sara R, Hagendoorn M, Marom O, Hughett P, Macy L, Turner T, Bajcsy R, Posner A, Gur RE. A method for obtaining 3-dimensional facial expressions and its standardization for use in neurocognitive studies. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods* 2002; 115:137-143.

[2] Kohler CG, Turner TH, Gur RE, Gur RC. Recognition of facial emotions in neuropsychiatric disorders. *CNS Spectrums* 2004; 9(4): 267-274.

[3] Kohler CG, Turner T, Stolar NM, Bilker WB, Brensinger CM, Gur RE, Gur RC. Differences in facial expressions of four universal emotions. *Psychiatry Research* 2004; 128: 235-244.

[4] Silver H, Goodman C, Knoll G, Isakov V. Brief emotion training improves recognition of facial emotions in chronic schizophrenia. A pilot study. *Psychiatry Research* 2004; 128: 147-154.

Short Fractal N-Back (2 back)

Test Title: SFNB2

Current Version: 3.00

Cognitive Domain Tested: Attention and Working Memory

Test Description: The SFNB2 is a measure of attention and working memory. In this task, participants are asked to pay attention to fractal designs displayed on the computer screen, one at a time, and to press the spacebar according to one rule per set of trials. There are three sets of trials, each repeated twice during the test: 0- back, 1-back, and 2-back. During the 0-back, the participant must press the spacebar whenever they see a specific design on the screen. During the 1-back, the participant must press the spacebar whenever the design on the screen

is the same as the one displayed right before it. During the 2-back, the participant must press the spacebar whenever the design on the screen is the same as the one displayed before the previous one (i.e. in the series design A, design B, design A, the participant should press the spacebar on or immediately after the second design A). In all trials, the participant has 2500 ms to press the spacebar. The participant practices each rule once, in which they are allowed to make mistakes and then, when they complete all practices successfully, the task will begin.

Rules & Variables: The SFNB2 is scored based on the total number of true/false positives, median reaction time for all correct responses, and number of true/false positives and median response times for each of the three principles.

Scoring Variables Notes: * The scores presented on WebCNP are raw scores. * All time-based scores (e.g. Response Time) are given in millisecond units (ms). ScorVers = scoring-code version - particularly important when analyzing data as we update the scoring code with corrections or necessary adjustments. True Positives = spacebar press following the ruling principle (a correct response). False Positives = spacebar press not following the ruling principle.

Reference:

[1] Ragland, J.D., Turetsky, B.I., Gur, R.C., Gunning-Dixon, F., Turner, T., Schroeder, L., Chan, R., Gur, R.E. Working Memory for Complex Figures: An fMRI Comparison of Letter and Fractal N-Back Tasks. *Neuropsychology*, 16, 370-379, 2002.

[2] Cohen NJ, Ryan J, Hunt C, Romine L, Wszalek T, Nash C: Hippocampal system and declarative (relational) memory: summarizing the data from functional neuroimaging studies. *Hippocampus* 1999; 9:83–98

Digit Symbol Test

Test Title: DIGSYM

Current versions: digsym-a-2.00-ff and digsym-b-2.00-ff

Cognitive Domain Tested: Processing Speed and Relational Memory

Test Description: The DIGSYM is a measure of processing speed and relational memory. This test is modeled after the Digit-Symbol Coding and Digit-Symbol Recall tests. The test is composed of a coding block of trials and a memory block of trials. The participant's task is to decide whether the target paired symbol and digit, in the center of the screen, is the same as one of the nine reference paired digits and symbols at the top of the screen. The participant makes their selections with the mouse by clicking on the "Same" or "Different" buttons on the screen. The participant may complete as many trials as possible within 90 seconds (90,000 ms).

In the memory block of the task the participant is presented a single symbol and the number portion of the reference block (numbers 1-9 sequentially). The participants is now asked to determine which number the target symbol was paired with in the reference set using the mouse to click on the appropriate number button. The memory block of the task ends when the participant completes all 9 trials or after 30 seconds (30,000 ms) have elapsed.

There are two versions of this task as demonstrated at the top of the page. The two versions differ in the pairing between symbols and numbers (e.g., the number 2 is paired with a triangle in one version, but the number 5 is paired with a triangle in the other version). Visits 1, 3, and 5 use version “a”, while visits 2 and 4 utilize version “b”.

Rules & Variables: The test is scored based on the number of correct and incorrect trials completed within 90 seconds, divided into true/false positives/negatives and the median response time for each category. The memory block is scored on the number of correct and incorrect responses completed within 30 seconds and the median response time for both categories.

Scoring Variable Notes: • The scores presented on WebCNP are raw scores. • All time-based scores (e.g. Response Time) are given in second units (s).

Short Visual Object Learning and Memory

Test Title: sVOLT

Current Version: 4.00

Cognitive Domain Tested: Visual Object Learning and Memory

Test Description: The sVOLT is a measure of visual object learning and memory. It was designed as a spatial analog of the California Verbal Learning Test. The sVOLT includes only the first set of trials of a series of 7 sets from the full version (VOLT) [1]. In the first part of this test, participants are shown 10 three-dimensional Euclidean shapes that they will be asked to identify for both immediate and delayed recalls (delayed recall = sVOLTd). During the immediate recall (sVOLT), participants are shown a series, one at a time, of 20 three-dimensional Euclidean shapes - the 10 shapes they were asked to memorize mixed with 10 novel shapes. The participant’s task is to decide whether he/she has seen the shape before by clicking with the mouse on one of four buttons: “DEFINITELY YES”, “PROBABLY YES”, “PROBABLY NO” and “DEFINITELY NO”. (NOTE: The original sVOLT had only two response choices: “YES I have seen the shape” and “NO I have not seen the shape.”). Participants have 20 seconds to select a response before the test moves on to the next trial. There are two forms of the sVOLT: the sVOLT-A and sVOLT-B. Visits 1, 3, and 5 use version “a”, while visits 2 and 4 utilize version “b”. NOTE: There are five classes of objects: triangles, squares, pentagons, hexagons and octagons. For each class, there are 2 figures in both study stimuli (5 x 2 = 10), and foils (5 x 2 = 10) for a total of 20 shapes during the test trials [1]. All stimuli have a geometric blue two-dimensional shape within the three-dimensional figure. The three-dimensional shape, two-dimensional blue shape and its location must be remembered in order to correctly answer test trials.

Rules & Variables: The test is scored based on the number and median response time of true/false positive/negative responses. The total correct and median response times of total correct and total incorrect responses are given, as well as the median response time of all responses.

Scoring Variable Notes:

SVTTP = "YES" responses to shapes that belong to the 10 shapes the participant was asked to study (correct responses).

SVTTN = "NO" responses to shapes that do not belong to the 10 shapes the participant was asked to study (correct responses).

SVTFP = "YES" responses to shapes that do not belong to the 10 shapes the participant was asked to study (incorrect responses).

SVTFN = "NO" responses to shapes that belong to the 10 shapes the participant was asked to study (incorrect responses).

* The score ranges are not standardized. Normative data for your project is not accounted for in the scores presented by the variables above.

References:

[1] Glahn DC, Gur RC, Ragland JD, Gur RE. Reliability, performance characteristics, and construct validity and initial application of the visual object learning test (VOLT). *Neuropsychology* 1997; 11:602-612.

[2] Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Turner TH, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: I. Methodology and validation in healthy people. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):766-776.

[3] Gur RC, Ragland JD, Moberg PJ, Bilker WB, Kohler C, Siegel SJ, Gur RE: Computerized neurocognitive scanning: II. The Profile of schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 25(5):777- 788.

Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

Fluid Biomarkers

Release: 4.0, May 2025. DOI: [10.15154/5wdf-9136](https://doi.org/10.15154/5wdf-9136)

Change Log:

- Participants added: the dataset now includes **2290** unique participants
- Data include visits from baseline up to and including month 2.

Selection criteria:

- Fluid biomarkers also include a multitude of additional checks to ensure that values fall within reasonable ranges and barcodes are entered properly. This includes scanning the database for volumes that exceed 1.1 millimeters, blood draw dates that are entered as being later than the dates that the vials were sent to the lab, processing times that exceed 480 minutes, and more. Rack barcodes are also checked to make sure they are in the proper formats and are not duplicated between participants.

Known Issues:

No known issues at this time.

Standard Operating Procedures for data collection:

Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Fluid Biomarkers Team. (2025). Standard Operating Procedures for Fluid Biomarker Acquisition in the Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Schizophrenia Program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10632951>

List of Instruments:

Instrument	Short Name
Vitals Assessment (Current Health Status Form)	vitas01
Daily Diary	dailyd01
Medications History	medhi01
Clinical Lab Tests Part II	clinlabtestsp201

General Information

The Fluid Biomarkers protocol consists of a range of measures selected based on the consensus of leading experts in the field of clinical high-risk for psychosis.

The following documentation describes the overall contents of various instruments used in the AMP-SCZ project and the instruments are available for download.

Instrument Descriptions

Vitals Assessment (Current health Status form)

The Current Health Status form collects information on height, weight, blood pressure, heart rate, and body temperature. Information on activity and inflammatory conditions is also collected including sleep and wake times, occurrence of last meal and/or beverage, tobacco and/or marijuana use, and menstrual period, the presence of any inflammatory condition (illness in the last month, acne (Investigator Global Assessment of Acne (IGA) Rating Scale), sunburn ("Rule of Nines" sheet to calculate the percent body area involved), and physical activity. A medication log collects information on current medications, any new medications, including (OTC or prescription) anti-inflammatories, pain medicine, allergy and/or cold medicine, diet pills, vitamins or other supplements, and antibiotics or steroids and records when any of these medications was last taken. Finally, information on COVID-19 infection and vaccination is collected.

Daily Diary

The Daily activity and Saliva Sample Collection Form collects information on a wide range of daily activities including food, alcohol, drug intake, behavioral issues, relationship issues, sleep, mood, anxiety. Information recorded for saliva collection includes: sample collection times, volumes, whether the study participant had a snack, meal or beverage other than water, if he or she has brushed/flossed his or her teeth in the past 45 minutes, or if she or he has had any water to drink within 10 minutes of each sample.

Medications History

Medications History records medication history, current medications, any new medications, including (OTC or prescription) anti-inflammatories, pain medicine, allergy and/or cold medicine, diet pills, vitamins or other supplements, and antibiotics or steroids and record when any of these medications was last taken.

Clinical Lab Tests Part II

CBC with differential form collects a wide range of blood measures including, Hematocrit (Hct), Hemoglobin, Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), Platelet Count Result, White Blood Cell Count (WBC), Neutrophil Count, Lymphocyte Count, Monocyte Count, Eosinophil Count, and Basophil Count.